

WinWin4 WorkLife

D2.2 Report on state-of-the-art, research gaps and conceptual diagram

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WORK PACKAGE N° 2

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R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, etc.	

Dissemination Level		
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CO	Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement	
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Project summary

WinWin4Worklife (WW4WL) envisions to enable healthy, inclusive and sustainable remote working arrangements (RWA) in Europe by combining employer and employee perspectives into a single framework. The project has five key objectives and outcomes:

- 1) To gain an interdisciplinary understanding of how the private and work spheres interact when working remotely;
- 2) To assess which living and working conditions ensure a healthy work-life balance in RWA for both men and women living in urban, rural, and cross-border areas;
- 3) To develop forecasting models of the impacts of different scenarios of RWA on mobility, land use, air quality, noise, and health;
- 4) To enhance knowledge on the role of culture, regional context and welfare systems in the uptake of RWA by employees and employers; and
- 5) To develop a comprehensive set of evidence-based spatial policies for a sustainable implementation of RWA, based on co-creation processes with stakeholders and citizens.

To do so, WinWin4WorkLife will collect novel and comprehensive data in 5 European countries (DE, FI, LU, PT, SK), selected to represent different welfare systems, housing and labour markets, and cultural norms towards remote work.

Data collection consists of an employer survey focused on organizational support for RWA, impacts on skills retention and productivity, and intentions to relocate; and an employee survey complemented by interviews and a time use app covering employee circumstances, gendered RWA experiences, impacts on work-life balance and mental health, as well as residential or job relocation, and social security and taxation issues. This quantitative and qualitative data will feed custom-made spatial forecasting models to assess wider urban/rural regeneration, environmental and health impacts.

Close and continuous engagement with planning, policy, business, and institutional stakeholders will ensure concrete and context-sensitive policy actions and measures for the sustainable uptake of RWA in Europe.

Executive summary

This report provides a comprehensive literature review of the state-of-the-art on social, economic, and spatial impacts of the different types of remote work defined in D2.1 *Lexicon on remote work*. It is part of Work Package 2 of the WinWin4WorkLife project and serves as a basis for other work packages in the project.

The review concentrates on understanding the impacts of remote working arrangements (RWA) on employees, employers, society, and the environment before the COVID-19 pandemic (since 2015) and the current situation since 2020 (post-pandemic). It includes a systematic literature review of academic research from various disciplines, supplemented by an examination of grey literature, including EU regulations and policies, as well as reports from international organizations such as the OECD and Eurofound.

The review is organized into three main impact areas of RWA: social and cultural (Section 3), economic (Section 4), and spatial and environmental impacts (Section 5). It also addressed current knowledge gaps (Section 6). Insights gained from the current literature review contributed to the development of a conceptual diagram that presents a holistic and integrated view of RWA impacts from the perspectives of employees, employers, and society, including their causal chains and potential feedback loops (Section 7). This diagram serves as the basis for further analysis in the project.

The main highlights of this systematic literature review regarding the impacts of RWA on society are:

- **Impacts on mental health and well-being:** Remote work can have both positive and negative effects on mental health. Positive factors include flexibility and support from leadership, while negative factors include work overload and technostress. Gender disparities are evident, with women, especially mothers, facing greater challenges in balancing work and family responsibilities.
- **Economic impacts:** Remote work has led to increased digital up-skilling and changes in employer attitudes towards flexible work arrangements. It has also highlighted inequalities in remote work opportunities across sectors and socio-demographic groups. Remote working arrangements are used by firms to attract talent and manage skills shortages, but they also present challenges such as managing remote employees and ensuring productivity.
- **Spatial and environmental impacts:** Remote work influences urban and rural areas differently, potentially reducing commuting but also causing rebound effects like increased non-work trips and higher energy use at home. The presence of digital nomads can impact local economies and contribute to gentrification, while multi-local living could influence urbanization trends.
- **Policy and regulation:** There is a need for better coordination in policies related to remote work, particularly concerning mental health, economic inequalities,

and spatial impacts. Some EU states have implemented the “right to disconnect” to address work-life balance, but broader regulatory improvements are needed to address the complexities of remote work.

In conclusion, this systematic literature review illuminates the multifaceted impacts of remote work arrangements on society, highlighting the need for nuanced policies and practices that address both the opportunities and challenges presented by the evolving reality of remote work.

Table of content

Acknowledgements	3
Project summary	3
Executive summary	4
Table of content.....	6
List of Figures.....	9
List of Tables	9
Abbreviations and acronyms	10
1. Introduction	11
1.1. Setting the scene.....	11
1.2. Recent developments of RWA.....	11
1.3. The role of RWA in society	13
1.3.1. Employee perspective	13
1.3.2. Employer perspective.....	14
1.3.3. Spatial perspective	14
1.4. Objectives of the literature review.....	16
2. Methodology.....	17
2.1. Definitions of RWA.....	17
2.2. Literature review approach.....	17
2.2.1. Defining clear review focus areas	18
2.2.2. Defining a harmonized search process.....	19
2.2.3. Defining a harmonized article screening process.....	20
2.2.4. Defining a harmonized review table and reviewing.....	22
2.3. Keywords used	23
3. Social and cultural impacts of RWA.....	26
3.1. Mental health and well-being	26
3.1.1. Well-being	26
3.1.2. Burnout.....	27
3.1.3. Stress, loneliness, and isolation	28

3.1.4.	Inequalities.....	29
3.2.	Work-life balance.....	30
3.2.1.	Quality of time.....	30
3.2.2.	Daily rhythms and household task arrangements.....	33
3.3.	Mental health impacts in policies and regulations.....	35
4.	Economic impacts of RWA.....	37
4.1.	Uptake of RWA.....	38
4.1.1.	Willingness for RWA.....	38
4.1.2.	Willingness to offer RWA.....	39
4.2.	Support for RWA.....	40
4.2.1.	Organizational support.....	40
4.3.	Productivity.....	41
4.3.1.	Employer-related factors and firm characteristics.....	41
4.3.2.	Employee-related factors and workforce characteristics.....	42
4.4.	Skills shortage and digital skills.....	43
4.4.1.	RWA and digital up-skilling.....	43
4.4.2.	Willingness to offer RWA as a recruitment tool to deal with skills shortage.....	44
4.5.	Wages.....	45
4.5.1.	RWA impacts on wages.....	45
4.6.	Taxation and social security.....	47
4.6.1.	Cross-border tax and transfer arrangements.....	47
4.7.	Economic impacts in policies and regulations.....	48
4.7.1.	Teleworkability.....	49
4.7.2.	Inequalities.....	50
5.	Spatial and environmental impacts of RWA.....	52
5.1.	Activity and travel behaviour.....	52
5.1.1.	Impact of RWA for travel behaviour.....	52
5.1.2.	Impact of RWA for daily activities.....	56
5.2.	Location decisions.....	57
5.2.1.	Employees' willingness to relocate residences.....	57
5.2.2.	Employees' willingness to relocate workplaces.....	58
5.2.3.	Employers' willingness to downsize and/or relocate offices.....	59

5.3.	Environmental impacts.....	60
5.3.1.	Physical activity	60
5.3.2.	Emissions.....	62
5.4.	Socio-spatial impacts.....	63
5.4.1.	Socio-spatial inequality due to RWA.....	63
5.5.	Specific case studies.....	65
5.5.1.	Cross-border mobility.....	65
5.5.2.	Digital nomadism and gentrification	66
5.5.3.	Multi-locality and second homes.....	67
6.	Main knowledge gaps	70
6.1.	Gaps in social and cultural impacts of RWA.....	70
6.2.	Gaps in economic impacts of RWA.....	71
6.3.	Gaps in spatial and environmental impacts of RWA.....	75
7.	Conceptual diagram.....	80
8.	Conclusion.....	85
9.	References.....	89
9.1.	Directives and regulations.....	89
9.2.	Policy papers, reports, and surveys	89
9.3.	Academic references.....	91
Annex 1	118

List of Figures

Figure 1: Yearly distribution of RWA articles 1970–2024 in Scopus.....	12
Figure 2: Example of a PRISMA workflow diagram.....	22
Figure 3: Simplified conceptual diagram.....	80
Figure 4: Part of the conceptual diagram capturing employee’s perspective.	81
Figure 5: Part of the conceptual diagram capturing employer’s perspective.....	82
Figure 6: Long term impacts of RWA for employer in (a) and employee in (b).	83
Figure 7: Policy concept	84

List of Tables

Table 1: Distribution of review focus areas.....	19
Table 2: Overview of screened, excluded, and reviewed articles.....	25
Table A1. Search queries for the social and cultural impacts of RWA.....	118
Table A2. Search queries for the economic impacts of RWA.	119
Table A3. Search queries for the spatial and environmental impacts of RWA.....	121

Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Short description
AI	Artificial intelligence
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
DCHE	The Danish Committee for Health Education
DOI	Digital object identifier
EBRD	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
EPFL	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne
EU	European Union
EU-LFS	EU Labour Force Survey
EWCTS	European Working Conditions Survey
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GFP	Global Forum on Productivity
GPS	Global Positioning System
ICT	Information and communications technology
ILO	International Labour Office
IT	Information technology
IST-ID	Associação do Instituto Superior Técnico para a Investigação e Desenvolvimento
JRC	European Commission Joint Research Centre
LISER	Luxembourg Institute of Socio-Economic Research
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
PRO	Prolepsis Institute
RWA	Remote working arrangements
TUM	Technical University of Munich
UH	University of Helsinki
UM	Maastricht University
UNIZA	University of Žilina
UPM	Technical University of Madrid
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
WFH	Working from home
WFS	Working from somewhere
WFA	Working from anywhere
ZEW	Leibniz Centre for European Economic Research

1. Introduction

1.1. Setting the scene

Remote work arrangements (RWA) offer flexibility in terms of location and frequency, encompassing opportunities where employees operate outside conventional office settings for at least some of their work hours (Spreitzer et al., 2017). Though remote work has been a topic of research for decades (Pliskin, 1997), the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the shift towards such arrangements. Prior to the pandemic, the share of employment in the EU that was potentially remotable (around 37%) was much greater than the actual prevalence of remote working (15%) (JRC, 2020a). As a result of the pandemic, both the demand for and provision of RWA have increased (Aksoy et al., 2022; Alipour et al., 2021; OECD, 2021a), indicating that RWA will play a crucial role in the future of work in certain industries (Barrero et al., 2021; Dingel & Neiman, 2020; Erdsiek & Rost, 2022). The frequency of working from home during the pandemic is positively associated with the willingness to continue working remotely in the future (Deole et al., 2023). Some workers are even prepared to give up 5.1% of their salary for the option to work from home, favouring a hybrid model of 2–3 days a week over a fully remote setup (Lewandowski et al., 2022). Another study indicates that employees in the EU would prefer to work remotely for 1.7 days per week, in contrast to the 0.7 days anticipated by employers (Aksoy et al., 2022). Key factors such as satisfaction, productivity, trust, and costs play crucial roles in the adoption of RWA by both employees and employers. Despite the increasing prevalence of RWA, its broader social, economic, and spatial implications require further examination, particularly in the context of post-pandemic evaluations, which remain limited thus far.

1.2. Recent developments of RWA

The COVID-19 pandemic has not only resulted in a proliferation of studies regarding RWA (see Figure 1, below), but also reshaped the discourse surrounding RWA, transitioning from viewing it primarily as a means to enhance work-life balance to focusing on its broader social, economic, and spatial implications. Understanding these impacts is crucial as European countries aim to promote inclusive and sustainable growth, ensuring that a diverse array of employees, employers, and communities can benefit from RWA while mitigating potential adverse effects on vulnerable populations and minimizing negative environmental and spatial consequences.

Initially, many employers viewed remote work optimistically as pandemic lockdowns began, but as the situation evolved, a renewed interest in in-person work emerged. Conversely, many employees express a preference for continuing remote work (Pan & Shaheen, 2022). Such differences between employers and employees highlight uncertainties about the future of work. Moreover, the pandemic period has revealed

significant potential spatial impacts of RWA. Many organizations reassessed their need for office space, with some opting to reduce their central office size and establish smaller, satellite offices instead (Hensher et al., 2023). Remote workers have altered their daily activities and travel patterns considerably (Arranz-López & Soria-Lara, 2022; Van Acker, 2022), with some choosing to relocate further from their places of employment (Duque-Calvache et al., 2021). However, the extent of these spatial changes, as well as the opportunities and threats for urban, rural, and cross-border areas are not yet fully understood (De Vos, 2020; van Wee & Witlox, 2021).

Figure 1 shows the yearly distribution of published academic articles from a Scopus database search performed with RWA terms (see Section 2.3) between 1970–2024. Research on RWA began to accumulate in the 2000s but exploded during the pandemic, with 18,607 of 29,447 articles (63%) published between 2015–2024 and 14,788 (50%) between 2020–2024 (highlighted in Figure 1). At the time of writing this report in July, there were already more than 2,000 articles published in 2024.

Figure 1: Yearly distribution of RWA articles 1970–2024 in Scopus.

1.3. The role of RWA in society

1.3.1. Employee perspective

Studies exploring the social impacts of RWA indicate varied outcomes on aspects like work-life balance, mental health, and productivity. Some studies found positive effects of RWA on work-life balance (Ferrara et al., 2022), due to increased flexibility in scheduling, more efficient rest periods, decreased time in meetings and commuting, and better time management (Asgari et al., 2023; Rubin et al., 2020). This can lead to reduced conflicts between work and personal life (Rubin et al., 2020), thereby improving mental health, job satisfaction, and overall happiness (Gueguen & Senik, 2023). Remote work can also promote mental well-being by providing employees a sense of autonomy and empowerment, as employees are trusted to manage their own time and workflow, especially when supplemented by organizational support making them feel useful and valued (Gueguen & Senik, 2023; Bertoni et al., 2021; Pelly et al., 2022; Vander Elst et al., 2017). Productivity may increase in remote settings due to lesser time spent interacting with colleagues, greater autonomy, culturally varied trust levels, improved decision-making capabilities, effective digital tool utilization, and the “Hawthorne effect” where awareness of observation boosts performance (Barrero et al., 2021; Deole et al., 2023; Angelici & Profeta, 2023; Brucks & Levav, 2022; Kim et al., 2021; Martin et al., 2022a). However, these positive outcomes are strongly influenced by the availability of a suitable and quiet home working environment (de Abreu e Silva, 2022).

On the other hand, RWA may negatively affect work-life balance and productivity, particularly for individuals in environments with abundant distractions, uneven distribution of household tasks, caregiving responsibilities, inadequate workspace, or lacking necessary technology (Asgari et al., 2023; Bertoni et al., 2021). Challenges may be magnified due to increased digital monitoring, information overload, and diminished in-person interactions which can complicate maintaining work-life boundaries (Antón et al., 2023; Brucks & Levav, 2022; Martin et al., 2022a; Martin et al., 2022b). Those with a negative RWA experiences can encounter work-life balance difficulties, concentration issues, social isolation, loneliness, and increased household and care responsibilities. This is especially true for women, potentially exacerbating gender inequalities, and for workers with young children (Ferrara et al., 2022; Rubin et al., 2020).

Finally, social inequities that exist due to the digital skill divide, such as income inequality, are likely to be exacerbated by an increase in RWA. The demand for digital skills witnessed a 23% increase in 2020 (Cedefop, 2020), yet in December 2019, 15% of workers considered themselves insufficiently digitally skilled to do their job (Eurobarometer, 2020). Disparities are particularly marked across occupations and between EU countries (JRC, 2020b). Although the pandemic has partly bridged the digital skill gap concerning gender and age, it has concurrently widened the gap linked to educational levels (Martin et al., 2022a).

1.3.2. Employer perspective

To effectively implement RWA, employers may need to adapt their management approaches. Nonetheless, transitioning to RWA can offer multiple advantages for companies. As discussed above, RWA can foster productivity and efficiency, as evidenced by the lack of productivity differences during the pandemic (Beck & Hensher, 2021). Additionally, while virtual interactions may generate fewer and less creative ideas, the ideas generated are often of higher quality (Brucks & Levav, 2022). Moreover, RWA allows companies to tap into a broader talent pool, facilitating the recruitment of more skilled employees from diverse locations (Brucks & Levav, 2022). This is notably beneficial for businesses seeking specific skills or expertise that aren't readily available in their local area. The broadened talent pool not only grants access to a wider skill set but also potentially reduces salary costs if employees are based in regions with lower living costs (Brucks & Levav, 2022). On the other hand, accessing top talent might require offering compensation for remote work-related expenses such as heating, electricity, and internet. Employers might save on business-related travel expenses as more activities shift online, lessen real estate costs due to reduced space requirements, and decrease overheads like heating and electricity (Brucks & Levav, 2022). Despite these benefits, adopting RWA also raises concerns for employers, particularly in maintaining team cohesion, upholding company culture, and managing logistical issues posed by different time zones and regional cultural differences (Brucks & Levav, 2022).

1.3.3. Spatial perspective

The expansion of RWA is likely to significantly influence spatial dynamics, particularly concerning employee mobility. The reduction or elimination of daily commutes can lead to substantial benefits such as time and cost savings, decreased CO₂ emissions, and reduced health risks associated with air pollution, traffic accidents, and noise (Brucks & Levav, 2022; Beck & Hensher, 2021; Shortall et al., 2022).

These impacts are crucial in urban settings, where concerns over traffic congestion and air quality are major concerns (Beck & Hensher, 2021). However, an unintended consequence of RWA might be an increase in non-work-related travel, potentially affecting traffic patterns, transportation modes, and travel distances (Mouratidis et al., 2021; Ravalet & Rérat, 2019; Staves et al., 2023). Additionally, research indicates that remote workers may choose to live further from their workplaces, accommodating longer commutes when necessary, therefore possibly increasing their total travel distance during a typical workweek compared to non-remote workers (Ravalet & Rérat, 2019).

Changes are also anticipated in residential mobility due to the flexibility offered by RWA, enabling individuals to live in environments that align more closely with their personal preferences. The impact and scale of these changes will vary depending on individual preferences. For some, this might mean moving to suburban areas, drawn

by preferences for more space or proximity to nature (Mouratidis et al., 2021; de Abreu e Silva & Melo, 2018). This could lead to a decline in demand for commercial office space in urban areas, potentially leading to lower commercial real estate prices, fewer jobs in sectors like food service and retail that rely on office workers, and diminished use of public transport systems as fewer workers commute into urban areas. Services might follow moving economic activity away from cities, revitalizing suburban areas (Beck & Hensher, 2021). Additionally, a suburban revitalization could trigger an increase in the demand for residential properties, potentially exacerbating socio-spatial inequalities. It could also result in higher CO₂ emissions and longer commutes for service workers in sectors that cannot be performed remotely, as they might have to adapt their travel patterns to new job locations in these suburban areas.

On the other hand, individuals with RWA who prefer urban living, proximity to amenities, and cultural venues may prioritize these factors over proximity to traditional workplaces. This preference could contribute to increased real estate prices in city centres, potentially creating affordability issues for lower-income residents. Additionally, there might be an increased demand for both formal and informal spaces that support remote work, such as co-working spaces or coffee shops (Shortall et al., 2022). If urban dwellers with RWA have convenient access to workplaces, services, and leisure activities all within close range of their residences, urban planning concepts like the “15-minute city” that emphasize resilience, sustainability, liveability, and health could become more feasible (Allam et al., 2022).

Ultimately, however, the effect of remote working on urban sprawl might be ambiguous. Studies suggest that while individuals with suburban preferences show positive attitudes towards remote working, those with preferences for urban living tend to view it less favourably (de Abreu e Silva, 2022). Especially in suburban areas, the rise in RWA could facilitate a hub-and-spoke model, where companies rent smaller office units in local hubs closer to where employees live. This satellite office model can provide professional spaces that help separate work from home life, foster social interactions, and decrease commute times and traffic congestion (Asgari et al., 2023).

The spatial impacts of RWA are further influenced by the type of RWA, particularly regarding preferred work locations. For example, those working from home may seek larger living spaces to accommodate home offices, potentially moving to suburban areas where such spaces are more readily available. Conversely, individuals who work from alternative locations outside of the home may prefer living in areas with a variety of accessible commercial venues, like coffee shops or co-working spaces. These spatial impacts might influence the rural and urban futures both nationally and globally. For example, “digital nomads” engage in geoarbitrage – residing in places with lower living costs while earning higher wages from more economically developed countries. This can potentially impact processes of transnational gentrification and contributes to a rebalancing of income disparities between countries (Holleran, 2022).

1.4. Objectives of the literature review

The integration of private and work spheres through RWA necessitates a comprehensive examination of the associated concerns. In the WinWin4WorkLife project, we address the concerns from an interdisciplinary approach using mixed methods. This strategy enhances the alignment with the EU's political priorities, which include the Green Deal, fostering a Europe fit for the digital age, and promoting an economy that benefits all citizens – leaving no person nor place behind.

The objectives of Work Package 2 of the WinWin4WorkLife project are multifaceted: In Deliverable D2.1 *Lexicon on remote work*, we focus on refining the terminology related to remote work to ensure clarity and consistency across various discussions. In Deliverable D2.2 *Systematic literature review on the impacts of remote work*, we build a comprehensive inventory of journal articles, working papers, reports, policy briefs and other literature, which creates a robust knowledge base that will support the empirical research conducted in Work Packages 4–6. Lastly, In Deliverable D2.3 *Conceptual diagram*, we refine and update the conceptual diagram for the WinWin4WorkLife project, ensuring that it effectively represents multiple disciplinary perspectives and current understanding of RWA dynamics. This report includes D2.2 *Systematic literature review on the impacts of remote work* and D2.3 *Conceptual diagram*.

WinWin4WorkLife is committed to bridging the existing research gaps by generating up-to-date contemporary data on the social, economic, and spatial impacts of RWA. This effort will make significant strides in understanding how remote work can be optimized to serve wider economic and social goals effectively.

2. Methodology

2.1. Definitions of RWA

Remote work is one of the most widely used terms for work arrangements in which employees do not commute to a central place of work, such as an office, but instead work from a location of their choosing (which is often their home). Remote work can be defined as *employment where individuals perform their job tasks from a location outside of a traditional office setting, often utilizing digital tools and communication technologies to interact with others inside and outside their organization* (Shirmohammadi et al., 2022).

Telework seems to be the most prominent alternative for remote work, but the terms are slightly different. The International Labour Office (ILO, 2020) describes their differences as follows:

“Telework is a subcategory of the broader concept of remote work. It includes workers who use information and communications technology (ICT) or landline telephones to carry out the work remotely. Similar to remote work, telework can be carried out in different locations outside the default place of work. What makes telework a unique category is that the work carried out remotely includes the use of personal electronic devices.”

Besides remote work and telework, our review of RWA includes various more specific terms, which are listed in Section 2.3, below. All terms were jointly agreed upon with partners when developing the deliverable D2.1 *Lexicon on remote work*.

2.2. Literature review approach

Deliverable D2.2 *Systematic literature review on the impacts of remote work* consists of a systematic literature review on RWA impacts from three broad dimensions:

1. Source type
 - a. scientific articles
 - b. reports and policies
2. Broad impact type
 - a. social and cultural
 - b. economic
 - c. spatial and environmental
3. RWA perspective
 - a. employee
 - b. employer

Altogether 12 partner institutions of the WinWin4WorkLife project contributed to the systematic literature review, so there was a need to divide the review to smaller tasks. To have a comprehensive overview, with few overlaps, there was also a need to have one harmonized review methodology that all partners followed. For this, we took a four-step approach:

1. Defining clear review focus areas
2. Defining a harmonized search process
3. Defining a harmonized article screening process
4. Defining a harmonized review table and reviewing process

It is worth noting that a systematic literature review was realistic only for scientific articles, whereas the review on reports and policies was more flexible. We developed separate instructions for the reports and policies review (see below).

2.2.1. Defining clear review focus areas

Based on the project kick-off meeting, an online meeting on February 26th, 2024, and emails between partners, we divided the systematic literature review for scientific articles into more specific focus areas under broader “impact types”: Social and cultural, Economic, Spatial and environmental, and Specific case studies (see Table 1, below). Each partner was assigned one or more focus areas, considering their overall project tasks and their preferences indicated during the project kick-off meeting. Review focus areas for policies and reports had their own focus areas, which partners could further specify given their overall project interests (see Table 1, below).

In general, each focus area was one separate review conducted by one partner. In cases where a focus area had more than one partner, the partners coordinated and agreed on whether they (a) further divided the focus area into narrower foci and did separate reviews of the literature with different literature queries in Scopus, or (b) divided the review workload after making a joint initial search query of the focus areas in Scopus.

Table 1: Distribution of review focus areas.

RWA impact type	Specific focus area	Partner(s)	
Social and cultural: Impacts on the private sphere	Mental health and well-being Burnout, stress, loneliness, isolation, and inequalities	PRO	
	Work-life balance Quality of time	VUB	
	Daily rhythms and household task arrangements	EPFL	
Economic: Impacts on the work sphere	Uptake of RWA Willingness for RWA	LISER	
	Willingness to offer RWA	ZEW	
	Support for RWA Organizational support	LISER	
	Productivity Employee productivity	LISER	
	Employers' concerns about their workforce productivity	ZEW	
	Skills shortage and digital skills Office vs. RWA	LISER	
	Willingness to offer RWA as a recruitment tool	ZEW	
	Bargaining power RWA impacts on wage offers	ZEW	
	Taxation and social security Cross-border tax and transfer arrangements	UM	
	Spatial and environmental: Impacts on cities and rural areas	Activity and travel behaviour Impact of RWA on travel behaviour	UNIZA
		Impact of RWA on daily activities	UPM
		Location decisions Employees' willingness to relocate residences - Residential relocation - Residential preferences	LISER/IST-ID
Employees' willingness to relocate workplaces		LISER/IST-ID	
Employers' willingness to downsize and/or relocate offices		LISER/IST-ID	
Environmental impacts Physical activity		TUM	
Emissions		UNIZA	
Socio-spatial impacts Spatial segregation and social inequality due to RWA		UH	
Specific case studies		Cross-border mobility	LISER
		Digital nomadism and gentrification	IST-ID
	Multi-locality and second homes	UH	
Reports and policies review	Mental health and well-being	DCHE	
	Economic impacts	ZEW	
	Teleworkability	UNIZA	

2.2.2. Defining a harmonized search process

Once each partner had a clear focus area (or several) for the literature review, we developed a harmonized article selection methodology for everyone to follow. For the systematic search of scientific articles, partners took the following steps:

- **Source selection.** We chose only one database, deeming Scopus the best option given that compared to Web of Science, Scopus covers more scientific journals from social sciences and approximately 99 % of the journals indexed in Web of Science are listed in Scopus (Singh et al., 2021). Google Scholar would

have required more screening time, which was unfeasible due to the relatively short time allotted for the systematic literature review.

- **Literature identification.** Partners used a harmonized search query, which consisted of three components. Terms and keywords were linked to (1) remote working arrangements, (2) which perspective was examined (employer or employee), and (3) what impacts were studied. The search query was thus formulated as:

(RWA keywords) AND (PERSPECTIVE keywords) AND (IMPACT keywords)

The first two components (RWA and perspective) consisted of predefined fixed keywords. RWA was a query subset of remote working arrangement terms studied in the project. The final fixed set of RWA keywords came from D2.1 *Lexicon on remote work* (see also Section 2.3, below). The perspective query subset focused on either the employer or the employee perspective or both, depending on the review focus area. For the impact component, however, partners were to determine and add their own focus area specific keywords. Section 2.3 lists the used keywords and Annex 1 lists the full search queries for each review focus area.

- **Search and exporting of results.** Finally, partners made the Scopus searches for articles using the search queries outlined above. The title of the article, the keywords, and the abstract text were included in the search. Partners then exported the lists of the articles that resulted from the Scopus queries as .CSV files, which included the following information: Author(s); document title; year; DOI; abstract; author keywords.

For the search and review of reports and policies, we had to adopt a different methodology as it was not feasible to conduct a systematic review. Finding sources and selecting reports and policies were open for partners to propose based on their prior knowledge of such reporting. Aspects that could be reviewed included (a) how RWA was defined in policies, regulations, or reports, (b) How RWA was covered in regulations and policies regarding e.g., tax, health, or social security issues. Partners engaged in a manual read-through of EU-level and national-level documents, including only documents from official government websites.

2.2.3. Defining a harmonized article screening process

After exporting the initial article lists from Scopus, partners screened whether each article was relevant or irrelevant for their specific review focus area. They used an AI tool called *ASReview* to help in screening, especially in cases of more than 100 articles to manually go through. *ASReview* is a tool specifically designed for systematically screening scientific articles, and it learns from user feedback and continually organizes the remaining list of articles so that the most relevant articles are shown next (van de

Schoot et al., 2021). In addition to providing a link to a video to all partners showing how *ASReview* works,¹ we defined the following short instructions for using *ASReview*:

- **STEP 1:** Import the exported .CSV file from Scopus into *ASReview*.
- **STEP 2:** Select 1–5 relevant and irrelevant articles by hand to “warm up” the AI tool.
- **STEP 3:** Start reviewing abstracts of articles ranked in order of relevance by the AI tool (relevant or not).
- **STEP 4:** Stop reviewing when you have labelled 20 articles in a row as “irrelevant” (you can see this in the “analytics” tab). This means the rest of the articles are very likely irrelevant to you.
- **STEP 5:** Export the dataset (choose “relevant only”) from *ASReview* as an Excel file.

After performing this initial screening, partners used a four-phase selection process to identify the final set of relevant articles following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) Statement (Page et al., 2021). Besides relevant subject matter, partners used the following inclusion criteria:

- Only empirical articles (no literature reviews, conceptual articles, etc.)²
- Only articles published between 2015–2024 (before and after COVID-19)
- Only articles published in English
- Only articles with full-text access available
- For some focus areas, only articles with a geographical focus on Europe

For geographical focus, we initially set a common course of including only studies focusing on Europe, but some reviews eventually decided to include all studies. This was due to some focus areas generally not disclosing the geographical focus area of the studies.

The PRISMA workflow diagram is shown in Figure 2 below, using the example of “multi-locality and second homes” review focus area. The Scopus keyword search for the impact of multi-locality and second homes on remote work arrangements initially produced 41 records, of which we deemed 24 as relevant based on manual screening of the abstracts. After excluding those that were published before 2015 (3) and those that were not empirical (7), not in English (1), or not focusing on Europe (2), we first included 11 articles in the systematic review. After reading the full text of the articles, we excluded one more as irrelevant, resulting in the final sample of 10 articles included in the systematic literature review for this specific focus area.

¹ <https://youtu.be/k-a2SCq-LtA>

² We made an exception for the focus area “taxation and social security” to include all kinds of articles, as research in the field is overwhelmingly non-empirical.

Figure 2: Example of a PRISMA workflow diagram.

2.2.4. Defining a harmonized review table and reviewing

To be able to combine the different focus area reviews from all partners into one harmonized review, we determined a set of fixed review questions for all partners. This could then be complemented with additional focus-area-specific questions by each partner, if they determined additional important information had to be included. For this reason, partners filled out an Excel spreadsheet containing the following items of each article that they reviewed:

1. Basic article information
 - a. Author(s)
 - b. Publication year
 - c. Title
 - d. DOI (or link)
 - e. Keywords

- f. Abstract
- 2. Eligibility questions (yes / no, only review if all yes)
 - a. Empirical study
 - b. English language
 - c. Full access
- 3. Review questions
 - a. Type of RWA studied? (WFH / WFS / WFA)
 - b. Main term(s) used for the RWA?
 - c. Study year(s)?
 - d. Study country/countries?
 - e. Study setting? (e.g., urban, rural)
 - f. Study subject? (e.g., employees, employers)
 - g. Population subgroup? (e.g., city inhabitants, company employees)
 - h. Sample size?
 - i. Methodological approach? (quantitative / qualitative / mixed)
 - j. Data collection method(s)? (e.g., survey, interview)
 - k. Impact(s) of RWA studied?
 - l. Analysis method(s)? (e.g., regression, discourse analysis)
 - m. Main findings regarding impact(s)?
 - n. Inequalities regarding RWA that emerged? (e.g., gender, age, education, residential location, company size, company location)
- 4. Focus-area-specific questions

Reviewing began by ordering articles by publication year, with the newest articles first. The focus was on two time periods: the post-COVID period (2020–2024) and the immediate pre-COVID period (2015–2019). Considering the recent impact of other societal developments in addition to the pandemic, such as technological advancement and digitalization, we deemed it appropriate to limit the pre-COVID period to five years. However, partners also kept older articles from the Scopus searches in the review tables for general meta-analysis. Similarly, they did not delete non-eligible articles from the Excel tables, but instead ordered them to be at the end of the list to not disturb review process.

For transparency within the project regarding what articles in each focus areas were reviewed, all partners uploaded the completed review tables to the project folder on SharePoint.

2.3. Keywords used

We formulated the final query for the systematic literature review search in Scopus as: *(RWA keywords) AND (PERSPECTIVE keywords) AND (IMPACT keywords)*. The input for the RWA keywords that we used in the literature search in Scopus came from D2.1 *Lexicon on remote work*. Partners performed the searches between March–June 2024.

The list of RWA keywords was:

- "co-working space"
- "coworking space"
- "digital nomad*"
- "digital workplace"
- "distance work*"
- "distributed work"
- {e-work}
- {e-working}
- "flexible work"
- "flexible workplace"
- "home-based work"
- "home office"
- "hybrid work"
- "location-independent work"
- "mobile office"
- "mobile work"
- "multi-locat* work"
- "remote job"
- "remote work"
- "satellite office"
- "second home"
- telecommut*
- telework*
- "virtual work"
- "work* from anywhere"
- "work* from home"
- workation
- workcation

The list of PERSPECTIVE keywords for the employer perspective was:

- company
- corporation
- employer
- enterprise
- firm
- mnc
- mne
- multinational
- organization

The list of PERSPECTIVE keywords for the employee perspective was:

- employee
- individual
- personnel
- staff
- team
- worker

The explanations for the search functions were:

1. The search is not case sensitive.
2. A hyphen is considered a space.
3. US/UK spelling variants and plurals are automatically included.
4. For multi-word terms, use "standard" quotation mark (not "curly" quotation mark).
5. For exact terms, use {curly brackets}.
 - e.g., "e-work" will retrieve thousands of articles containing "... i.e., work ..." while {e-work} will retrieve only the articles containing this exact term.
6. An asterisk * will replace multiple characters.
 - e.g., "digital nomad*" also includes "digital nomadism".
7. AND retrieves articles which contain **all** of the search terms.
8. OR retrieves articles which contain **any** of the search terms.
9. (Brackets) work in the same way as in mathematics.

Table 2 presents an overview of screened, excluded, and reviewed articles. Annex 1 presents all the conducted Scopus queries with different keyword combinations we used for the literature review.

Table 2: Overview of screened, excluded, and reviewed articles.

Impacts of RWA		Articles		
		Screened	Excluded	Reviewed
Social and cultural: Impacts on the private sphere	Mental health and well-being	276	171	105
	Burnout, stress, loneliness, isolation, and inequalities	276	171	105
	Work-life balance	2,811	2,750	61
	Quality of time	193	162	31
	Daily rhythms and household task arrangements	2,618	2,588	30
Economic: Impacts on the work sphere	Uptake of RWA	3,689	3,600	89
	Willingness for RWA	1,823	1,756	67
	Willingness to offer RWA	1,866	1,844	22
	Support for RWA	1,685	1,673	12
	Organizational support	1,685	1,673	12
	Productivity	3,133	3,035	98
	Employee productivity	1,055	1,003	52
	Employers' concerns about their workforce productivity	2,078	2,032	46
	Skills shortage and digital skills	868	859	9
	RWA and digital up-skilling	116	108	8
	Willingness to offer RWA as a recruitment tool	752	751	1
	Bargaining power	358	353	5
	RWA impacts on wage offers	358	353	5
Taxation and social security	231	208	23	
Cross-border tax and transfer arrangements	231	208	23	
Spatial and environmental: Impacts on cities and rural areas	Activity and travel behaviour	1,036	961	75
	Impact of RWA on travel behaviour	384	346	38
	Impact of RWA on daily activities	652	615	37
	Location decisions	371	349	22
	Employees' willingness to relocate residences			
	- Residential relocation	109	101	8
	- Residential preferences	12	8	4
	Employees' willingness to relocate workplaces	143	139	4
	Employers' willingness to downsize and/or relocate offices	107	101	6
	Environmental impacts	457	418	39
	Physical activity	315	290	25
Emissions	142	128	14	
Socio-spatial impacts	128	123	5	
Spatial segregation and social inequality due to RWA	128	123	5	
Specific case studies	Cross-border mobility	36	36	0
	Digital nomadism and gentrification	382	367	15
	Multi-locality and second homes	41	31	10
Total number of articles examined		15,502	14,934	568

3. Social and cultural impacts of RWA

Social and cultural impacts of remote work arrangements are related to individuals' private sphere, leading to well-being changes. From the employee perspective, impacts range from mental health and well-being issues such as loneliness (O'Hare et al., 2024), isolation (Gerich, 2023), stress (Consiglio et al., 2023), and burnout (Niebuhr et al., 2022) to work-life balance issues such as the intensity of work and the fragmentation of the workday. When working remotely, individuals often lack in-person interaction with colleagues, which may lead to feelings of isolation and disconnect (Schade et al., 2021), and can also experience "Zoom fatigue" due to excessive video conferencing (Nurmi & Pakarinen, 2023).

Remote work also alters the traditional work-life boundaries, potentially affecting family dynamics and personal relationships, as the home becomes an extension of the workplace. Although increased flexibility may reduce stress (Freire & Alves, 2023) and improve work-life balance, the lack of physical separation between work and personal life can also lead to extended work hours and difficulty "unplugging," potentially increasing the likelihood of burnout (Consiglio et al., 2023). Additionally, without proper ergonomic home office setups, physical discomfort and strain can contribute to mental health issues. However, the elimination of commuting can reduce daily stress and provide more time for personal activities, contributing to better mental health (Seinsche et al., 2023). Not all remote workers will or can deal with this in the same way and inequalities in the use of remote work and its impact might exist.

The employer's perspective on these issues is not adequately investigated, especially regarding concerns about their workforce's well-being when working remotely; the literature on this topic is limited and scarce. Employers can, for example, promote a healthier work-life balance by encouraging employees to set specific work hours and take regular breaks or by providing resources and tools for stress management and mental health support. Managers who are concerned about employee well-being in remote work should encourage virtual social interactions and team-building activities to foster a sense of community and combat feelings of isolation. In addition, remote work entails a cultural shift towards valuing autonomy and output over presenteeism, which encourages more trust-based management.

3.1. Mental health and well-being

3.1.1. Well-being

There is a scarcity of studies exploring the impact of remote work on well-being during the pre-COVID era. Among these, the largest study conducted across 35 EU countries revealed that the overload experienced by homeworkers had an overall negative impact on well-being (Zappalà et al., 2022). Work-family conflict was found to have a

negative relationship with work engagement and well-being. However, ter Hoeven & van Zoonen (2015) found that the flexibility of WFH positively correlated with well-being.

Full-time employees surveyed in the UK during two phases – before the onset of COVID-19 and in April 2020 during the lockdown period – reported poorer mental and physical health while working from home. The use of electronic communication during leisure time, except for email engagement even after work hours, was identified as the primary reason for this decline (Braithwaite et al., 2023). Supportive leadership appears to play a significant role in the well-being of remote workers (Lundqvist et al., 2022), and effective communication and a balanced work-life equilibrium have been identified as crucial for ensuring the well-being of employees working remotely. Additionally, proficient communication moderates the relationship between organizational skills and well-being (Petcu et al., 2023). Further supporting these findings, Keightley et al., (2023) indicate that the blurring of physical and psychological boundaries between work and leisure might compromise well-being.

3.1.2. Burnout

Several studies have shown that burnout symptoms are linked to remote working, both positively and negatively. In a web-based large survey carried out in Belgium in 2020, quite many Flemish employees reported experiencing extended remote work due to COVID-19, but more than half reported that this mode of working helped them lower the chance of burnout (Moens et al., 2022). In Germany, during the early stages of COVID-19, working from home was associated with higher competence and better work engagement. However, the increase in working hours resulted in more stress-related symptoms, including mental exhaustion and burnout (Niebuhr et al., 2022).

Although similar findings were evident in other studies, the results suggest the significant role of mediating factors. In Austria in 2021, a survey of 808 professionals working in Finance, Insurance, and IT revealed that inadequate equipment was associated with burnout, family conflict, perceived technostress, and feelings of social exclusion (Gerich, 2023). Technostress also appears to be a key factor related to burnout, highlighting the importance of training and organizational support. In Italy, 349 participants working from home reported technostressors related to burnout. These technostressors were also positively related to anxiety stressors, which in turn contributed to depressive moods and anxiety, leading to increased levels of burnout and poorer psychological health. Burnout was found to fully mediate the relationship between technostressors and depressive mood and partially mediate the relationship between technostressors and anxiety symptoms. Interestingly, those who felt more self-efficacy in e-work were less at risk for burnout, further indicating technostress as a key contributor to burnout (Consiglio et al., 2023). Focusing on the potential intermediary variable of voluntariness, results indicated that when working from home was voluntary, as seen in individuals in Portugal, there was no significant

correlation between engagement and burnout. However, different results showed that when remote work was involuntarily imposed, there was an increase in individuals' exhaustion and engagement (Dias et al., 2022). Profession, lifestyle, and related skills may serve as additional mediating factors. Contrasted with a random representative sample drawn from the Flemish workforce in Belgium (Moens et al., 2022), a cross-sectional study revealed a lower occurrence of burnout symptoms among researchers and staff of a civic university (Kiss et al., 2023).

The predominant factor associated with burnout was notably poor work-life balance (Gazem et al., 2023). Additionally, lacking a quiet work environment and concerns regarding long-term work situations were significantly linked to burnout (Kiss et al., 2023). Other mediating factors explored included personal characteristics such as age, resilience, self-regulation, and demands and resources during the pandemic. In the Netherlands, age and resilience were found to be directly linked to higher job resources, work-life balance, and a positive outlook, but not with workload (Scheibe et al., 2022). A Polish employee survey indicated a negative correlation between resource gains and burnout and a positive correlation with resource losses. This trend, however, was more pronounced for those who worked on-site rather than remotely (Stasiła-Sieradzka et al., 2023). Despite their limited sample size, qualitative studies shed light on more nuanced factors that may play a mediating role. These studies suggested that the pace of work was more likely to be associated with burnout than after-hours work, and the relationship with one's manager was also significant (Sjöblom et al., 2022).

A systematic review of the psychological impacts of new ways of working indicated that while it can enhance worker engagement, work-related flow, and connectivity, it also interferes with the boundary between work and home, increasing burnout and mental demands (Kotera & Correa Vione, 2020).

3.1.3. Stress, loneliness, and isolation

Many studies have investigated the links between remote work and stress, loneliness, and isolation. Olsen et al. (2023) found that job demands, characterized by the difficulty of work tasks, were positively correlated with stress levels. Conversely, factors such as effectively managing work-life balance and receiving support from leaders were negatively associated with stress. Interestingly, employees who worked more extensively from home reported lower job stress levels than those primarily working in the office (Olsen et al., 2023). A large survey conducted among academic staff in Italy in 2020 uncovered key factors influencing general psychological distress during the pandemic. Clarity of work objectives and adequacy of equipment were found to decrease levels of psychological distress, serving as protective factors amid the challenges and uncertainties of transitioning to new work methods. Conversely, experiencing work-family conflicts and concerns about economic uncertainty and future job prospects were associated with increased psychological distress (Macciotta et al., 2022).

Among 520 mental health professionals in the UK who worked remotely, half reported a moderate or greater degree of loneliness, along with higher stress levels and lower workplace satisfaction (O'Hare et al., 2024). Similarly, Norwegian workers who transitioned to remote work during COVID-19 restrictions reported increased loneliness and decreased work engagement. However, remote working was found to be negatively associated with bullying, which in turn was positively correlated with loneliness but negatively correlated with work engagement. This intriguing finding suggests that remote work may have both positive and negative effects, potentially reducing bullying or serving as a protective factor against it (Bollestad et al., 2022). In France, employees working from home during the second lockdown displayed two distinct psychological profiles: "solitary" and "affiliative." The "solitary" group reported higher levels of loneliness and lower levels of job satisfaction (Michinov et al., 2022). In Lithuania, survey respondents reported that men were more prone to experiencing anxious thoughts, feelings of loneliness, and headaches, particularly among those who were parents (Raišienė et al., 2023).

Findings from Hungary in 2020 revealed that workers did not feel isolated from their colleagues due to supportive co-worker assistance, cohesion, and the use of modern communication techniques (Pataki-Bittó & Kun, 2022). Conversely, an Estonian survey in 2021 revealed individuals working from home experienced higher levels of social isolation compared to traditional office settings, particularly due to the absence of informal chats and feelings of exclusion. However, in certain cases, remote workers felt less socially isolated than those in single and shared cell offices or small open-plan offices, particularly when they had colleagues to share thoughts with and rely on for support (Aidla et al., 2023).

Similar findings emerged from a qualitative study involving women in Spain, including uncontrolled emotions, irritability, distress, and both mental and physical exhaustion. These women also expressed a lack of motivation for their work and feelings of loneliness (Loezar-Hernández et al., 2023).

3.1.4. Inequalities

Various inequalities have been explored in relation to remote working, encompassing differences in age, parental status, migration status, interethnic conflict, and discriminatory behaviour. Age has emerged as a significant factor, with studies investigating its impact on remote work experiences revealing that older individuals often face heightened stress due to challenges such as adapting to technology and managing increased caregiving responsibilities (De Andres-Sanchez et al., 2023). Similarly, parental status has been a critical focus, with parents encountering difficulties in balancing work and caregiving duties (Pataki-Bittó & Kun, 2022). Research underscores the differential impacts of the mandatory transition to remote work on males and females, with males experiencing heightened anxiety and longer work hours, while females are more susceptible to anxiety, loneliness, and fatigue.

Notably, females, particularly mothers, are more prone to burnout and anxiety as they navigate the dual responsibilities of work and childcare (Raišienė et al., 2023). In Northern Italy, heavily affected by the pandemic, depression levels were higher among women unable to work remotely, leading to emotional exhaustion (Grandi et al., 2021).

3.2. Work-life balance

3.2.1. Quality of time

The quality of time can be assessed using both subjective and objective measures. Subjective measures relate to the perception of time, time pressure, or intensity. Objective measures related to the quality of time include duration, timing, sequence, fragmentation, and contamination of time. It is important to note that “objective” refers to the method used to collect data on people’s time use. The most objective measures are derived from time diaries in which individuals record all their daily activities for at least 24 hours in close to real-time. This approach partially overcomes recall, confirmation, and social desirability biases (Minnen et al., 2023).

Objective time allocation

Occasionally working from home leads to spending less time on paid work during those days at home, as indicated by several studies (e.g., Powell & Craig, 2015; Giménez-Nadal et al., 2020; Restrepo & Zeballos, 2020; Pabilonia & Vernon, 2022; Giménez-Nadal & Velilla, 2024). However, Pabilonia & Vernon (2022) found that remote workers tend to work longer hours on the days they do go into the office. Additionally, the timing of work shifts when working from home allows workers to plan their work more flexibly. Remote workers work less during traditional “core” working hours and more during evening hours (Powell & Craig, 2015; Giménez-Nadal et al., 2020; Pabilonia & Vernon, 2022). This flexibility is often used to accommodate home needs. Many remote workers, especially those who regularly work from home, spend more time on leisure and unpaid work, even during typical working hours (Giménez-Nadal et al., 2020; Restrepo & Zeballos, 2020; Giménez-Nadal & Velilla, 2024), although gender differences do exist. Not having to go to the office allows remote workers to spend less time on commuting and personal care (Pabilonia & Vernon, 2022; Restrepo & Zeballos, 2020). In summary, there is a shift in the objective allocation of time in terms of *duration*, meaning more working time on office days compared to home days, and in *timing*, meaning more shifting towards “non-standard” hours on home days to allow for more unpaid work and leisure time during “standard” hours.

Inequality in time allocation

The *timing* of work is central to studying inequality in RWA. Indeed, the impact of remote work on time use has primarily been examined from a gendered perspective, comparing female and male remote workers, as well as mothers and fathers who work remotely. Powell and Craig (2015) observed the most significant differences between regular remote workers and those who never work from home among women, primarily due to the time female remote workers dedicate to housework and childcare when working from home. Similarly, Giménez-Nadal and Velilla (2024) found that the reduction in paid work when working from home was more substantial for women than for men. Pabilonia and Vernon (2022) noted that female remote workers spent more time on sleeping and household care, while father remote workers allocated more time to primary childcare. The presence of a spouse at home also appears to influence time use, with more time spent on food preparation and eating and drinking when a spouse or partner is present (Restrepo & Zeballos, 2020). However, Derndorfer et al. (2021) discovered that during COVID-19 lockdowns, men only performed more housework proportionally when their partner was not present or both were working from home, while more time on childcare was only spent by remotely working men whose female partner did not work from home. These findings suggest more traditional gender roles when both partners are present (van Tienoven et al., 2023). Working from home during a lockdown, where schools and other institutions are closed, is not comparable to working from home in non-lockdown times. Craig and Churchill (2021) state that lockdowns create a significant amount of extra unpaid work (e.g., home schooling), which is predominantly shouldered by women.

In addition to gender, ethnicity may also play a significant role in remote working dynamics. Our review of the literature revealed only one study that investigated differences in remote working and time allocated to work from home before and during the pandemic based on ethnicity (Hoxhaj & Miti, 2023). The authors found that Asian and Latinx women worked more from home and logged more hours when working from home compared to White American women during the pandemic. The substantial difference between Asian and White American women is attributed to the higher educational attainment of Asian women, their concentration in sectors and jobs that are more conducive to remote work, and the anti-Asian sentiment following the COVID-19 outbreak (Hoxhaj & Miti, 2023).

Job function is another factor that might explain differences in time spent on work when working from home. According to Teodorovicz et al. (2022) managers from large firms spent significantly more time on work during the lockdown than non-managers from large firms. The workdays of these managers were longer and more fragmented due to spending more time in (online) meetings to substitute for some of the interactions that normally happen in the office.

In summary, the inequality in the impact of RWA on time use has primarily been studied from a gender perspective. The COVID-19 pandemic served as a “natural experiment” that kept both women and men at home, highlighting existing

disparities. Even in this context, it appears that the potential for working from home to better align work and family responsibilities is more applicable to women than to men. Other inequalities, such as ethnicity and job function, tend to relate to the “teleworkability” (see Section 4.7.1) of the job, influencing how different groups can engage with remote work opportunities.

Objective and subjective quality of time

In addition to the duration and timing of activities, time-use diaries can also provide insights into quality indicators of time such as multitasking (e.g., measured by registering two activities simultaneously in a time diary) and fragmentation (e.g., measured by the number of interrupted episodes of a single activity in a time diary). Research confirms that working from home appears to increase both multitasking (Powell & Craig, 2015; Craig & Churchill, 2021) and the fragmentation of time (Powell & Craig, 2015; Pabilonia & Vernon, 2022). Women, particularly mothers, tend to multitask more often (typically combining work with childcare) (Powell & Craig, 2015; Craig & Churchill, 2021) and experience more interruptions during their workday (Pabilonia & Vernon, 2022).

These more objectively measured experiences can lead to subjective experiences related to time. Darouei and Pluut (2021) and Vesala and Tuomivaara (2015) found that remote work decreases the experienced time pressure. However, Thulin et al. (2019) observed an increase in time pressure among those who regularly work remotely. The differences between studies are based on the context of remote work and the type of remote worker. Unregulated and occasional forms of remote work, as well as contexts of lockdowns with children at home, might lead to more time pressure (Thulin et al., 2019; Leroy et al., 2021; Bartolj et al., 2022). The location of remote work also appears to play a role. Having a dedicated, unshared workspace can decrease nonwork interruptions while working (Leroy et al., 2021). A rural remote working retreat decreases work interruptions as well as time pressure (Vesala & Tuomivaara, 2015). Compared to home-based e-workers, mobile e-workers experience more work-related stress and higher work intensification (Curzi et al., 2022).

Again, gender differences are also observed. Women experience more interruptions than men during remote work due to greater nonwork responsibilities (Leroy et al., 2021; Craig & Churchill, 2021) and have less autonomy over how they manage their time while working from home (Tufă & Negut, 2023). Men appear to be more insulated from household duties when working from home than women, making their experience of time less influenced by these responsibilities (Tufă & Negut, 2023).

In summary, objective measures indicate that working from home leads to increased multitasking and fragmentation of time use. Subjectively, this is experienced as heightened feelings of time pressure, time stress, or a sense of being rushed. Women tend to experience these objective and subjective indicators more intensely than men.

Similar effects are observed for those who work from home occasionally, mobile e-workers, and remote workers without a dedicated workspace.

It is important to note that the remote workers studied in the literature on working from home are primarily white-collar, knowledge workers. These workers' roles are generally more conducive to a home office environment, and they often possess greater autonomy over their work schedules. Furthermore, many studies conducted as of 2020 have investigated the impact of remote work during lockdowns, during which the demographic of remote workers was likely more diverse than before. This shift prompts the question of how the dynamics of remote work have evolved post-COVID.

3.2.2. Daily rhythms and household task arrangements

A review of the literature from the perspective of daily rhythms and arrangements has shown that remote working is a powerful indicator of social inequalities and relations of domination, as well as of strategies for readjusting to household and family life. The literature review highlighted three dimensions. The first dimension concerns the quality of social relations, both in the domestic sphere and in relations with colleagues and employers. The second dimension relates mainly to relations of power and domination in the domestic sphere, particularly as regards the division of tasks within the couple. Finally, the third dimension suggests that remote working is a powerful vehicle for reorganising both tasks and power relations within the household and in relations with the employer.

Social impact of remote work

The literature review highlighted various social dimensions that influence the practical realities of everyday life on the one hand, and the well-being of individuals on the other. The first dimension mainly concerns cohabitation relationships in the domestic sphere. In this respect, the literature largely focuses on the quality of marital relationships, but also on relationships with children. Situations of loneliness and isolation are also an important issue in the literature. The social isolation caused by WFH can leave people feeling unwell and uncomfortable. Beyond the domestic sphere, the literature shows structural imbalances in the workplace. People who work remotely regularly are likely to feel isolated from their colleagues. The literature suggests that remote workers experience different working conditions in the workplace. This difference in treatment is also likely to generate a feeling of social isolation (Al Riyami et al., 2024). This effect may also be reinforced by the company's policy on remote working and the relationship between employees and their manager. In fact, the literature suggests that working remotely may cause managers to be suspicious of the productivity of employees working remotely. Conversely, employees are likely to show signs of discomfort depending on the control

arrangements and the relationship with their manager. More specifically, some studies show that remote working is potentially a limiting factor in careers. Indeed, WFH can potentially limit access to promotion and social and professional mobility (Kasperska et al., 2024).

Power and gendered dominations

As is well documented in the literature on power relations in the home, remote working situations are likely to generate significant tensions, particularly in the context of marital relations (Fan et al., 2023). On the one hand, remote working is likely to amplify gender inequalities. As the literature covering the lockdown period shows, remote work plays a mediating role which opens new negotiations in family arrangements (Elizabeth et al., 2023). Among the subjects of negotiation are the division of labour within the couple regarding the management of household tasks, the involvement of fathers in the management of children and the commitment to a non-gendered balance in the life of the couple (Derndorfer et al., 2021). Remote working thus appears potentially as a tool for negotiating and readjusting the rules of the game of everyday life (Inoue et al., 2024). This perspective also introduces the role of culture and values in negotiation methods and gender relations in the division of everyday tasks. In addition to the factors internal to the household that contribute to arrangements and negotiations, the literature also highlights the role of different types of emotional support. In this respect, friends and personal networks play an essential role. On the one hand, friends and family provide important support, particularly in managing day-to-day life. On the other hand, the quality of interpersonal relationships with work colleagues is just as important in providing emotional support. As a result, people who work remotely are more likely to feel happier if they receive emotional support from both their personal and professional environment.

Tensions between productivity and personal life

Analysis of the literature suggests that employees working remotely face a dilemma. Remote working involves a tension between the personal and professional spheres. As a result, remote workers are likely to feel a certain discomfort with their employer (Loh et al., 2023). This discomfort becomes clear when managers adopt a position of suspicion towards employees. The discomfort is also significant to the extent that company policies on remote work lack clarity. Furthermore, the lack of support from companies for their employees is highly likely to generate a great deal of stress and tension between the professional and personal spheres (Kismono et al., 2023). Conversely, a clear policy stance on the part of the company towards its employees and concrete support measures such as the provision of equipment for the workplace at home are powerful factors in reconciling the professional and personal spheres (Botha et al., 2023).

3.3. Mental health impacts in policies and regulations

We examined RWA policies across all EU member states to investigate the current landscape regarding the policy framework of RWA, and we also looked for any policy recommendations or frameworks in relation to the impact of RWA on mental health. We subsequently outlined several focus areas of the policies.

The main source for policies in relation to RWA can be found in the respective countries' various forms of labour codes. The general focus (with some exceptions; see below) of these policies is to ensure that RWA are included into the respective countries labour laws and regulations. The aim of these policies is to ensure that the responsibilities of both employers and employees are outlined and codified into the respective countries labour codes, laws, and regulations. The policies often outline under what specific criteria a person would have the right to work remotely, and how these arrangements should legally be outlined. These rights vary from country to country and are dependent on what type of policies the country applies to labour and labour conditions. In general, the focus of policies in relation to RWA seems to be revolving around labour regulations, and updating policies and codes, so that these include RWA.

The main findings of this policy review reveal that most of the EU member states have updated their labour policies to include RWA within the last couple of years. Most of these updates seem to have happened either during the COVID-19 pandemic or in its immediate aftermath. Notably most of these policies focus on regulations of RWA from an administrative standpoint and seldom include recommendations or next steps.

Most countries did not specifically mention mental health, in relation to RWA, and in general mental health did not seem to be a focus area for the policies revolving around RWA. One noteworthy exception is the *right to disconnect*. However, the right to disconnect was often not connected specifically to mental health considerations, although the connection is apparent.

The right to disconnect is an EU directive, which defines the right to disconnect as: *A worker's right to be able to disengage from work and refrain from engaging in work-related electronic communications, such as emails or other messages, during non-work hours*. The context for the right to disconnect can be found in directives from the European Parliament (*Directive (EU) 2019/1158*) and the European Council (*Directive 2003/88/EC*), as well as from the European Pillar of Social Rights (European Commission, 2021). The right to disconnect is also integrated into national policies of Belgium, France, Greece, Luxembourg, Malta, and Spain.

Moreover, some countries have established policies addressing several aspects of mental health in relation to RWA. Bulgaria outlines that the employer should try to ensure avoidance of isolation and ensure social engagements for people working remotely. Belgium has identified three pillars for the right to disconnect: I. Overview of the practical modalities for the application of the right to be unavailable outside

working hours; II. Guidelines for using digital tools in such a way as to safeguard rest periods and holidays; and III. Education and awareness campaigns for employees on the sound use of digital tools and the risks associated with an “always on” culture.

Slovakia has introduced measures to both enhance the right to disconnect and to combat the isolation of remote workers. Employees who work from home or engage in remote work have the right to not use their work equipment during their designated daily and weekly rest periods, unless they are scheduled for standby or overtime, or during holidays and other non-working periods. If an employee chooses not to work during these times, the employer cannot consider it a breach of obligations. Additionally, to prevent remote workers from feeling isolated, employers are encouraged to facilitate opportunities for these employees to visit the workplace and interact with their colleagues whenever feasible.

Denmark has issued recommendations aimed at maintaining a healthy psychosocial work environment, emphasizing that these guidelines should also apply to remote workers. However, these recommendations have not yet been formalized into policy. Meanwhile, France has enacted the right to disconnect, which is designed to promote a healthy work-life balance and protect employees from the stress of being compelled to remain online and work outside of regular hours, particularly in remote working scenarios. This measure in France seeks to safeguard employees from the pressures of constant connectivity when working remotely.

Besides the policies of the EU member states, we also investigated policies from EU organizations and governing bodies. In general, it can be said that at a European level, there are few existing policies and even fewer strategies towards developing policies. However, documents and ideas point to similar or identical definitions and foundations, so while there is a general agreement on the basic definitions and principles related to remote work, there has been limited progress in developing a comprehensive framework of key performance indicators to evaluate the impact, progression, distribution, or potential of remote work.

The link between mental health and productivity is frequently mentioned, but impact on transportation, community activity, types of employment, or types of skills is rarely mentioned. There seems to be a consensus on the existence of a strong potential of a geographically flexible “gig economy,” but little analysis on the impact on labour markets, worker rights, urban planning, educational systems, or transport policies. Furthermore, if there exists a broader dataset or a key performance indicator system to monitor these changes and trends, it has not been made publicly accessible. This lack of comprehensive data and strategic planning indicates a need for a more structured approach to understanding and shaping the future of work within the EU framework.

4. Economic impacts of RWA

The economic impacts of remote work arrangements are related to the work sphere of individuals and organizations. From the employee perspective, willingness to work remotely can broaden employment options, and experience in working remotely may lead to an increase in the digital skills divide between those who can navigate the digital work realm and those who have difficulties with it. This can lead to uneven bargaining power of potential employees. In terms of productivity, many employees report increased productivity when working from home, as they experience fewer interruptions and no commute times. However, this varies by individual, and some may struggle with the distractions at home or lack of a work-like environment.

Even before the pandemic, RWA had gained in importance in the past two decades. However, as pointed out by Šmite and Moe (2024), RWA was considered a privilege and firms usually allowed only a small share of the workforce to work remotely until the pandemic hit. This drastically changed since March 2020 when RWA started to become much more prevalent and to be considered as a new normal (Lang & Hofer-Fischinger, 2022; Silva-C et al., 2019). The long-lasting shift towards more flexible work arrangements is deemed to have a multitude of economic consequences at the firm level, including management practices, productivity, wages, or coping with skills shortages (Kagerl & Starzetz, 2023; Angelici & Profeta, 2023; Arntz et al., 2022; Macaluso & Waddell, 2022). For instance, the firms' willingness to offer remote work options may become an important recruitment tool. Remote work arrangements could alleviate skills shortages by enabling employers to tap into a broader talent pool, reducing geographical barriers to employment (Davis et al., 2022; Soroui, 2021). However, this calls for comprehensive training and upskilling programs to ensure that employees are comfortable and capable of navigating digital work environments effectively. Recent studies find strong heterogeneity in employers' willingness to offer RWA depending on key factors such as firm size, management practices, degree of digitalization, and workforce characteristics (Kagerl & Starzetz, 2023; Silva-C et al., 2019; Šmite et al., 2023). Remote work can also lead to cost savings on office space and related expenses, but employers must invest in technological infrastructure and focus on additional training to support effective remote work (Allen et al., 2024; Boutros et al., 2023).

Cross-border remote work raises tax and social security implications for both employers and employees. Tax jurisdictions have differing rules on how income is taxed when the work is performed remotely for a foreign firm, which could result in tax liabilities and social security issues in multiple countries.

A better understanding of the economic impacts of RWA becomes more and more important for policymakers to make informed decisions. Consequently, an increasing number of policy reports focuses on the manifold consequences related to the recent shift towards more flexible work arrangements. These studies highlight potential positive effects on productivity and employee performance (Eurofound & ILO, 2017;

European Commission 2024; OECD, 2021b, 2022) as well as potential negative effects such as longer and more antisocial working hours (Eurofound 2020, 2022; ILO, 2021). In addition, recent policy reports highlight RWA's potential to intensify or alleviate existing inequalities, e.g., income inequalities and gender inequalities (OECD, 2017, 2022, 2023).

4.1. Uptake of RWA

4.1.1. Willingness for RWA

Prior to the onset of the pandemic, remote working was underutilised in industrialised countries. A limited proportion of workers engaged in remote work, and when they did, it was largely on an ad-hoc basis. Some studies indicated that individuals with higher levels of education, those with dependent children, those residing in urban areas or subject to long commutes, and those with multiple vehicles in their household were more likely to work remotely or to express a desire to do so (e.g., Vilhelmson & Thulin, 2016).

COVID-19 and the resulting restrictions on business operations and employee mobility have led to a significant increase in the number of companies and employees adopting remote working. During this period, remote working was, where possible, full-time and widespread. The pandemic period therefore enabled many workers to experiment with remote working and accelerated its take-up. Studies carried out at the end of this period suggest that remote working will continue to be a key aspect of business operations. Theoretically, the investments made by companies and employees in remote working, the effectiveness of remote working, and the less stigmatised status of remote workers compared to before the pandemic are all factors that point to the continued use of remote working (Barrero et al., 2021).

Empirically, the desire of remote workers to continue working remotely after the health crisis is based on survey data. Remote workers are seeking a hybrid form of work that combines on-site work and more frequent use of remote work than before the pandemic. They also express a preference for working solely from home, rather than from a third location or alternating between home and a third location (Asmussen et al., 2024). Some studies have indicated that most workers are willing to accept a significant reduction in remuneration in exchange for the opportunity to work from home on two or three days per week (Barrero et al., 2021; Lewandowski et al., 2022). The most frequently cited reasons for wanting to remote work are the absence of commuting, greater flexibility, and fewer interruptions (Benoit et al., 2023).

The literature shows that the desire to continue working remotely varies according to workers' socio-demographic characteristics. For instance, factors such as gender, level of education and income, disability, age, having dependent children, household size, geographical location and sector of activity are linked to the willingness to work remotely. However, it is likely that there will be considerable variation within a single

socio-demographic category. For instance, the correlation between the desire to continue working remotely and age differs according to family composition and the status of being a migrant (Barbour et al., 2021). In addition to socio-demographic characteristics, it has been suggested that the performance of employees working remotely influences their intention to continue remote work or not (Ameen et al., 2023). However, according to Prodanova and Kocarev (2022), productivity gains are not a sufficient condition for continuing to work remotely, unlike satisfaction levels. According to Kim (2024), organisational support can help to eliminate differences in the use of remote work, as in the case of gender differences.

4.1.2. Willingness to offer RWA

Before the pandemic, RWA were limited and often seen as a privilege (Šmite & Moe, 2024). The pandemic, however, shifted perceptions, making RWA a perceived personal right and establishing it as the new normal (Šmite & Moe, 2024). The necessity for social distancing highlighted the practicality and usefulness of remote work, influencing its broader adoption (Silva-C et al., 2019). Kagerl & Starzetz, 2023) and Knoesen et al. (2021) confirm that attitudes towards RWA have evolved, leading employers to continue offering remote work options post-pandemic. Lang and Hofer-Fischanger (2022) further demonstrate that the utilization of RWA remains above pre-pandemic levels, indicating a lasting change in workplace dynamics.

RWA are increasingly adopted by employers who weigh their potential benefits against perceived drawbacks. Employers recognize cost savings and employee retention as significant advantages of RWA (Soroui, 2021; Maietta & Gardner, 2022; Šmite & Moe, 2024). However, concerns about isolation and its impact on communication, business outcomes, and worker health are also noted (Babapour Chafi et al. 2022; Rossi & McLaren, 2022). Consequently, a hybrid model that combines remote work with office presence is favoured for its balanced benefits (Babapour Chafi et al., 2022; Kagerl & Starzetz, 2023; Šmite et al., 2023).

Moreover, the vast majority of studies, both pre- and post-pandemic, focus on the factors that affect employers' willingness to offer RWA (e.g., Babapour Chafi et al., 2022; Goñi-Legaz & Ollo-López, 2015; Gordon et al., 2015; Magda & Lipowska, 2022; Soroui, 2021; Stirpe, 2023). A general finding of these studies is a strong heterogeneity in employers' willingness to offer RWA depending on key factors such as firm size, management practices, degree of digitalization, and workforce characteristics.

Specifically, industry and firm size may affect RWA uptake. Kagerl & Starzetz, 2023) observed that larger firms are more likely to implement remote work in the long term. Conversely, Šmite et al. (2023) found no consistent patterns related to firm size or location, and Stirpe (2023) noted a reluctance in family-owned firms due to traditional managerial practices and a preference for in-person presence.

Managerial support and structured management practices are crucial for the successful implementation of RWA. Silva-C et al. (2019) emphasized the need for managerial backing, and Groenewegen and Hardeman (2023) discussed the importance of structured management practices. Also, digitalization and the use of technological tools are critical for the successful implementation of remote work. Silva-C et al. (2019) highlight the importance of information security tools in influencing managers' attitudes toward remote work adoption.

Employers also consider employees' preferences to increase worker satisfaction and employee retention. As employee preferences tend to differ by demographics, the workforce structure thus exerts some influence on the provision of RWA. However, firms may not only be willing to offer remote work to increase job satisfaction of the incumbent workforce. The use of remote work may also facilitate talent acquisition (Soroui 2021).

Apart from these factors, the willingness to offer RWA may also depend on employer preferences. Gordon et al. (2015) show that employers' past experiences with RWA affect their approach and have a lasting effect on their management practices. Knoesen and Seymour (2021) find that older managers have a higher preference for office work. Moreover, employers' positive attitude towards remote work also improves its efficiency, work control, and support, such as providing more equipment and training to employees (Pokojski et al. 2022). This may suggest a mutual self-reinforcement if positive attitudes increase firm performance under a RWA regime, which then again increases support for its widespread implementation.

Finally, Magda and Lipowska (2022) report differences by country with Continental and Nordic countries more likely to offer remote work options than employers in Central and Eastern European countries, potentially driven by country-specific attitudes towards RWA.

4.2. Support for RWA

4.2.1. Organizational support

To the best of our knowledge, few studies have examined the issue of organisational support for remote work. Most of the studies we have identified were conducted in the aftermath of the pandemic. They emphasise the significance of providing support for remote work, particularly in the form of hybrid working arrangements, accompanied by adapted managerial policies, with the objective of enhancing the productivity and satisfaction of remote workers. Zapata et al. (2024) argue that these organisational practices must be personalised.

Among the managerial practices identified by these studies as conducive to remote workers' productivity and effective remote work practices are the fostering of a climate of trust, professional advancement, goal setting and a training plan, reduced

perceived surveillance, fair approval and evaluation, and virtual networking activities (Zapata et al., 2024; Gerich, 2023; Baumann & Marcum, 2023). Furthermore, the quality of the equipment utilised by remote workers is also a significant factor (Gerich, 2023). As remote working has a direct impact on management, companies must provide training for their managers in remote working and encourage employees to report back to their managers efficiently (Gong et al., 2023). Furthermore, according to some studies, the company structure should be adapted to accommodate remote work by becoming less hierarchical (Contreras et al., 2020).

4.3. Productivity

4.3.1. Employer-related factors and firm characteristics

One of the key aspects that influences the productivity of employees working remotely is how they are managed. After the pandemic, there has been a greater emphasis on structured management practices, supportive organizational policies, and adaptive leadership to sustain productivity in remote work settings (Kagerl & Starzetz, 2023; Stoker et al., 2022). Underscoring the need for adequate management strategies, Korkeakunnas et al. (2023) found that remote work changed work routines and how teams work, leading in particular to faster decision making but focused on the output rather than how the work is carried out. Becerra-Astudillo et al. (2022) highlighted that communication with co-workers and supervisor trust improve productivity. Studying the role of human resource management practices, Aggarwal et al. (2023) found that clear job descriptions, continuous training, and performance evaluations are critical for productivity. At the same time, managers who allow autonomy and flexibility support better productivity in RWA (Allen et al., 2024). Angelici and Profeta (2023) confirmed that the flexibility to work from anywhere and adjust working hours to personal needs allows employees to simultaneously optimize their performance and improve their well-being and work-life balance, an important determinant of employees' productivity.

Technological adaptation plays a vital role in the success of RWA. Allen et al. (2024) and Martin et al. (2022a) emphasized that proficiency in digital tools and platforms is crucial for remote workers. Continuous technological training and support are necessary to ensure employees can effectively navigate the digital landscape, maintaining high productivity levels. Boutros et al. (2023) focused on adapting to the new normal brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic. Their research showed that remote work had a positive impact on firm performance and employee productivity, particularly within industries that could leverage digital tools effectively. Patanjali and Bhatta (2022) analysed the impact of work-from-home arrangements during the pandemic within the IT sector. Approximately two-thirds of IT employees reported increased productivity.

Various firm characteristics influence the productivity impact of RWA. Aksoy et al. (2022) examined global trends in remote work during the pandemic for 27 countries. They emphasized that the effectiveness of remote work varied widely across different countries and sectors. Regarding the role of the industry, technology and knowledge-intensive sectors generally report positive productivity outcomes (Błaszczyk et al., 2022; Patanjali & Bhatta, 2022). These sectors often have robust digital infrastructures that support effective remote work. But even traditionally on-site industries can benefit from remote work under certain conditions, as found by Fontaneda et al. (2023) for the manufacturing sector. Overall, companies with strong digital infrastructures and flexible work policies tend to see more positive impacts from RWA (Allen et al., 2024).

Firm size also plays a significant role, with larger firms having more resources to support remote work infrastructure than smaller firms (Monteiro et al., 2022; Kagerl & Starzetz, 2023). On the other hand, Kotey and Koomson (2021) and Boutros et al. (2023) found that small and medium-sized firms experienced highest increase in productivity, in particular when RWA are combined with flexible hours. These findings suggest that while large firms benefit from substantial resources, small and medium-sized firms may also experience significant productivity gains from remote work due to their adaptability and resource allocation.

The overwhelming share of articles found positive effects of RWA on productivity. However, studies also highlighted that the positive effects of RWA depend on the realisation of conducive conditions (Rodrigues et al., 2022). In fact, a few studies do not find positive effects of remote work on productivity. Morikawa (2022, 2024), Saurombe et al. (2022), and Tanpipat et al. (2021) find lower or comparable productivity at home compared to usual office work, indicating that the effectiveness of RWA depends on the specific employer's practices and firms' characteristics. And of course, the firm's workforce also influences how RWA will impact its productivity as we discuss in the following section.

4.3.2. Employee-related factors and workforce characteristics

Employee productivity is primarily assessed through surveys that include self-reported productivity questions. Many of these surveys aim to determine whether employees perceive themselves to be more, less, or equally productive when working from home compared to their productivity in a traditional office environment, yielding varied results. These studies often reveal negative impacts of working from home on productivity, highlighting challenges associated with adapting to a change in working arrangements (JRC, 2020c). Many studies investigating how employee-related factors influence productivity focus on employee well-being, which is discussed more extensively in Sections 3.1.1, 3.1.2, and 3.1.3.

While remote work has brought benefits for some, it has not consistently led to significant improvements in work performance, indicating major challenges in maintaining a good work-life balance and inequality among employees in benefiting from these new practices. Banerjee and Gupta (2024) emphasized that techno-overload and techno-invasion have negative impacts on employee productivity, suggesting that the technological demands of remote work can be a hindrance rather than a help if they are excessive. Martin et al. (2022a) also found that excessive information flow could increase stress. Therefore, a balanced approach of moderate remote work combined with office hours tends to lead to better productivity outcomes (Hoorweg et al., 2016).

The pandemic highlighted the critical importance of digital tools and infrastructure. Proficiency in using digital tools became a key determinant for remote work productivity (Martin et al. 2022a; Patanjali & Bhatta, 2022). The pandemic also highlighted demographic disparities, such as gender differences in productivity (Cui et al., 2022; Allen et al., 2024). Different subgroups of employees, categorized by work conditions, sectors, and demographic characteristics, experience varied impacts from remote work. Younger employees and those with more job autonomy often report higher productivity when working remotely. However, parents with young children, particularly mothers, report higher levels of stress and an increased unpaid workload, affecting their productivity (Beno and Hvorecky, 2021).

4.4. Skills shortage and digital skills

4.4.1. RWA and digital up-skilling

A study by Cedefop (2020) revealed that the demand for digital skills increased the most between 2019 and 2020 among the skills requested in online job offers. The development of remote working may provide an opportunity for employees to improve their digital skills, particularly those who report having a lower level of digital skills, such as women, older workers, and those with fewer qualifications.

To the best of our knowledge, only a few studies have examined the impact of remote working on employees' skills. The results of these studies indicate that remote working is associated with an increase in skills, particularly digital skills. For instance, König and Seifert (2022) found that older workers who worked exclusively from home during the period of confinement exhibited, all things being equal, a greater increase in digital skills than those who worked from home on a part-time basis. Some authors posit that the greater autonomy enjoyed by employees working remotely is a key factor in this observed increase in skills (Dima et al., 2020). Conversely, others argue that in the context of remote work, the development of employees' digital skills is more influenced by collaboration with colleagues than by direct instruction from superiors.

It can be observed that certain socio-demographic groups appear to benefit more than others from the positive impact of remote working on skills. Hauret et al. (2024)

demonstrate that the perception of digital upskilling during the period of social isolation is positively correlated with the status of being a woman, being at least 50 years of age, or holding at least a master's degree, in the absence of other confounding variables. According to these results, the lockdown contributed to narrowing the digital skill gap related to sex and age but widened the gap based on educational background.

4.4.2. Willingness to offer RWA as a recruitment tool to deal with skills shortage

The question of whether remote work arrangements can facilitate firms' ability to recruit new employees and to avoid skill shortages has gained considerable significance in light of the pandemic. The pandemic has led to a widespread shift towards remote work arrangements, which has in turn expanded the boundaries of local labour markets. This expansion might allow firms to tap into a broader and more diverse talent pool, transcending traditional geographic constraints. In addition, several recent studies show that employees value RWA as an amenity. This could enable firms to attract new employees by offering RWA, as they appeal to the non-financial job preferences of potential new employees. Despite these plausible reasons suggesting that RWA could be increasingly used as a recruitment tool, our systematic literature review yielded only a few articles focusing on such changes in the recruitment strategies of firms.

Davis et al. (2022) provide evidence that employers offer remote work to recruit and retain employees. Roughly 35 percent of firms with up to 500 employees in their survey study indicated that they offer remote work arrangements to recruit new employees. Among larger firms (501+ employees), this share even amounts to nearly 60 percent. In addition, the results show that employers who offer remote work to attract new employees also show a stronger propensity to expand the geographic reach of their recruitment efforts. At the time of the survey in late 2021, many firms also used remote work arrangements to retain existing employees.

In another survey, 155 in-house recruiters and HR professionals were asked whether they have made any changes to how they recruit workers in the last year (Macaluso & Waddell, 2022). Over 40 percent of firms indicated that they now allow for remote work arrangements when trying to recruit mid-skilled or high-skilled workers. Offering remote work is much less common for recruiting low-skilled workers (17 percent). Similar shares of firms indicated to offer flexible work hours to recruit new workers with the respective skill-levels. Finally, roughly half of the firms expanded their geographic reach of recruiting when trying to hire high-skilled workers. Extending the geographic area for hiring purposes is much less common for mid-skilled workers (35 percent) and low-skilled workers (17 percent).

Focusing on fully remote arrangements, Soroui (2021) finds that firms increasingly use remote work as a strategy to overcome regional talent acquisition challenges. The

study reveals that firms not only use fully remote work as a proactive talent acquisition strategy, but also use such flexible arrangements to retain highly valued employees. Similarly, Biea et al. (2024) found that small and medium-sized enterprises are getting creative with benefits packages focused on remote and hybrid work to improve work-life balance of existing employees and potential hires.

These existing studies that focus on RWA as a potential recruitment tool support the idea that firms use flexible arrangements to attract and retain employees. Specifically, employers are increasingly using RWA as a strategy to address local skills shortages and to broaden the geographic scope of their talent pool. In this manner, the shift to remote work induced by the pandemic, along with firms' adjustments to traditional search patterns, has led to the expansion of local labor markets. To prevent skills shortages, firms also utilize RWA to retain highly valued employees whose skills might be difficult to replace with new hires.

4.5. Wages

4.5.1. RWA impacts on wages

Whether RWA affect wages and whether such effects lead to minor or major inequalities between individuals is the subject of extensive research. From a theoretical point of view, RWA may give rise to either a wage penalty or premium, depending on the effects that RWA have on productivity and bargaining power. As laid out in Sections 4.3.1 and 4.3.2, most empirical studies point to positive productivity effects which should result in a wage premium for RWA usage. However, RWA may also affect the bargaining power of employers relative to employees. If employees attach a positive value to RWA, as suggested by the widespread preference for such work arrangements among employees discussed in Section 4.1.1, this should give rise to a compensating wage differential, resulting in a wage penalty. Hence, wage effects are ambiguous a priori. Moreover, wage effects may differ by sub-groups of workers as employers may perceive productivity effects and the bargaining power attached to RWA quite differently by gender or parenthood status.

Given this ambiguity, it is not surprising that empirical studies find rather mixed outcomes. Glass and Noonan (2016) find evidence for a wage penalty for working from home. Arntz et al. (2022) find a wage premium for working from home for fathers only, while for mothers, a positive income effect is driven by extended contractual working hours rather than increased wages when starting to work from home.

In fact, a key dimension of inequality looked at in the literature is the gender dimension and the effect of RWA on the gender wage gap, with multiple studies documenting differential impacts on men and women. Arntz et al. (2022) find significant gender disparities, with women experiencing less favourable wage outcomes compared to men. Still, their results suggest that, while RWA may not be a means of reducing the gender wage gap, it may still have a positive effect on the

gender income gap, as they find contractual hours among mothers to increase by more than 15% when starting to use RWA. Hence, wage effects of RWA do not seem to be uniform across employee groups, but instead depend on household characteristics.

There is also evidence that the wage effect of RWA is mediated not only by gender, but also by job type and firm characteristics. White (2019), for instance, shows that the wage differential between home-workers and office-workers has been declining, but persists for certain job types and demographics. This suggests that the implementation and acceptance of RWA across different sectors and roles can vary widely. As regards the role of the firm context, Kotey and Koomson (2021), look at the link between firm size and the financial returns from flexible work arrangements. They find that remote work has positive effects on the financial returns from labour, but only for medium-sized firms, potentially reflecting that large firms finding it more difficult to monitor their workers. This implies that the scale of the organization can significantly influence the financial outcomes of remote working policies and the corresponding bargaining power of employees.

In addition, there is some evidence that wage effects might also hinge on the employer's ICT equipment as such technologies may facilitate remote work and reduce the costs from monitoring remote workers. Kitagawa et al. (2021) present evidence for Japan that the stronger productivity decline among individuals who worked from home compared to those who worked onsite during the COVID-19 pandemic are due to poor WFH conditions.

Hence, the increasing diffusion of ICT equipment since the 1980s might also be a main cause for a declining wage penalty from RWA across time. White (2019) even observes a shift from a wage penalty in the 1980s to a wage premium in the 2010s for WFH, suggesting that firms face increasingly lower monitoring costs and cost advantages from reducing office space that they share with employees.

Overall, the interaction between remote work and compensation structures seems to be rather complex, depending on employee as well as employer characteristics. The literature on RWA reveals significant impacts on wages, with notable inequalities, particularly along gender lines. In addition, the diffusion of new technologies that facilitate remote work may improve the bargaining power by employees. Yet, there is a notable lack of post-pandemic evidence on the wage effects of RWA such that differences pre- and post-COVID are basically unknown. While RWA hold potential for promoting wage equity, their effects are mediated by a range of factors, including firm size, job type, and demographic as well as household characteristics.

4.6. Taxation and social security

4.6.1. Cross-border tax and transfer arrangements

Remote work poses a significant challenge for policymakers (Eurofound, 2022). Working from home can profoundly impact the applicable rules concerning taxation, social security, and labour law (Jorens, 2022; Bruurs, 2023). In terms of taxation, bilateral tax treaties generally apply, while for social security at the European level, *Regulation (EC) 883/2004* is relevant. This regulation is founded on the principle of free movement of workers (Verschuieren, 2022; Aceto, 2024). Both instruments involve different conflict rules, and the applicable regulations can lead to varying outcomes, potentially causing discoordination and influencing the net income of cross-border workers either positively or negatively. During the pandemic, it was possible to overlook applicable conflict rules. Post-pandemic, a framework agreement on social security under EU law was implemented (de Pauw & Verschuieren, 2023); however, this was not the case for taxation, which still relies on bilateral treaties. Some EU member states have established special bilateral arrangements concerning taxation and remote work (e.g., between Italy and Switzerland; Amaddeo, 2023), yet many states lack such agreements. A few articles specifically review remote work issues within individual states (e.g., Portugal: Martins & Taborda, 2023; Spain: de Azúa & Gil, 2023).

Some articles focus on the presence or absence of RWA. Discussions in these articles vary, with some addressing the issues faced by frontier workers (Niesten, 2022) and others exploring the challenges encountered by digital nomads (Pignatari, 2023; Ouro, 2023; Kostić, 2019). For frontier workers, typically two states are involved, whereas for digital nomads, the situation may involve more than two states. A key consideration for digital nomads is whether they maintain sufficient "nexus" with a residence or source state to justify the allocation of taxing rights to that state. The state of residency usually serves as the starting point for applying a tax treaty to allocate taxing rights on elements of income. An additional complexity for nomads is determining whether there is an employment relationship or a provision of independent services (Pignatari, 2023).

Regarding the existing rules for attributing taxation, physical presence currently serves as a crucial criterion. However, the applicability of this criterion in the context of WFH is under scrutiny (Ferrer, 2023). Schwarz (2023) questions whether the outcomes of allocating rights to tax the income of an employee in remote work situations are consistent with the benefit principle. This principle suggests that a taxpayer should pay taxes proportionate to the benefits received from public services in a state. Schwarz (2023) raises concerns about whether the states involved in the income-generating activity have the adequate capacity to tax that income.

Related to remote work concerning employers and companies is the concept of a permanent establishment. A permanent establishment, defined as the existence of a fixed place of business in the source state, serves as a mechanism to attribute taxing rights on an employer's profits to that state. Kostić (2019, 2021) advocates for the

introduction of a new form of permanent establishment, termed a workforce presence permanent establishment concept, specifically for scenarios involving working from home (also see Ferrer, 2023).

Another significant issue is the impact of cross-border remote working on substance requirements that deny certain tax benefits in cases deemed artificial, particularly concerning the dividend withholding tax exemption under *Directive 2011/96/EU*. Ravelli and Strik (2023) argue that these substance tests conflict with the principle of freedom of establishment. Additionally, the complex interactions between digital nomads, *Directive (EU) 2022/2523*, which ensures a minimum level of taxation, and the proposed “Unshell Directive” are also under discussion (Ouro, 2023).

4.7. Economic impacts in policies and regulations

As remote working arrangements become more widespread, it is crucial for policymakers to acknowledge their economic impacts to make informed decisions. The purpose of the policy papers in this section is to synthesize findings from economic research, contextualize them within the regulatory frameworks of countries or groups of countries (such as the EU), and provide policy recommendations.

Reports from Eurofound and the European Commission focus primarily on EU countries, except for a joint report from Eurofound and ILO (2017), which also includes five non-European countries. OECD reports cover various countries but still emphasize European nations, as most OECD members are European. These reports are often supplemented by European survey data, with major sources including the EU Labour Force Survey (EU-LFS), which provides extensive data on labour participation in the EU (Eurofound, 2022, European Commission, 2024), and the European Working Conditions Survey (EWCTS), used in Eurofound and ILO (2017) and Eurofound (2019, 2020). Additionally, OECD (2021b) incorporates data from the Global Forum on Productivity (GFP) to analyse the productivity and well-being impacts of remote work.

The effects of RWA can be ambiguous, depending on numerous factors. It is evident from the reports that changes in working regulations are necessary to incorporate new ways of working and ensure the positive impacts of RWA prevail (Eurofound, 2019 on working conditions; European Commission, 2022 on work-life balance). Interestingly, despite the widespread adoption of RWA during the pandemic, less than half of EU member states implemented regulatory changes (Eurofound, 2022). This might indicate that there are still regulatory gaps that need to be addressed.

Although many reports find that RWA increases productivity and employee performance in certain conditions (Eurofound & ILO, 2017; European Commission, 2024; OECD, 2021, 2022), these positive impacts might be offset by negative effects, such as longer and more antisocial working hours (Eurofound, 2020, 2022; ILO, 2021). A worsened work-life balance could potentially have serious long-term negative effects. Therefore, resolutions such as ensuring all workers have the “right to disconnect”

(Eurofound, 2022; European Commission, 2024) are necessary. A study by OECD (2020) identifies an inverted U-shaped relationship between efficiency and the amount of remote work, suggesting that a hybrid (part-time) work arrangement would be ideal to mitigate adverse effects of RWA and still benefit from it. The hybrid approach is also recommended by Eurofound & ILO (2017).

Three EU directives that are particularly relevant for remote workers are the “Working Time Directive” (*Directive 2003/88/EC*), the “Transparent and Predictable Working Conditions Directive” (*Directive (EU) 2019/1152*), and the “Work-Life Balance Directive” (*Directive (EU) 2019/1158*). It might be necessary to revisit those regulations in the light of the widespread adoption of RWA.

4.7.1. Teleworkability

Teleworkability refers to the extent to which the tasks associated with an occupation can be performed remotely, without requiring physical presence at a central workplace. This concept encompasses both the technical feasibility and the efficiency of performing work tasks from home or another remote location. The teleworkability index, as defined by JRC (2020a), considers various factors, including the nature of job tasks, the degree to which these tasks can be digitized, and the necessity for physical presence. Jobs that involve high levels of digital engagement and minimal need for physical interaction are deemed highly remotable (JRC, 2020a).

JRC (2020a) estimates that around 37% of jobs in the EU are potentially remotable, a figure significantly higher than the proportion of employees who worked remotely before the pandemic. The analysis of teleworkability across various sectors and socio-economic dimensions has revealed several important insights. First, certain sectors exhibit exceptionally high levels of teleworkability. For instance, the finance and ICT sectors show that 93% and 79% of jobs, respectively, can be performed remotely. Examples of highly remotable jobs include software developers, financial analysts, customer service representatives, and administrative assistants. Conversely, the least remotable jobs are found in sectors such as construction, manufacturing, retail, and food services, where physical presence is essential.

Teleworkability varies significantly across different countries, with Northern and Western European nations such as Sweden, Finland, and the Netherlands exhibiting higher levels of remotable jobs, where approximately 35–40% of jobs can be performed remotely. In contrast, Southern and Eastern European countries like Italy, Greece, and Bulgaria have lower levels of remotable jobs, with only about 20–25% of jobs being remotable. This variation is attributed to differences in industrial structure, digital infrastructure, and the occupational composition of the workforce. (JRC, 2020a). Dingel and Neiman (2020) found that about 37% of jobs in the United States could be done entirely from home, with significant variation across cities and industries. When this classification was applied to 85 other countries, it revealed that lower-income

economies have a smaller share of remotable jobs, often due to the higher prevalence of manual and service-oriented roles that require physical presence.

Some of the analysed reports also highlight several policies and regulations designed to enhance the teleworkability of jobs across various sectors and regions. The *Framework Agreement on Telework* (2002) provides foundational guidelines, emphasizing voluntary participation, equal treatment, and data protection. Investments in digital infrastructure, such as those promoted by the EU's Digital Agenda, aim for widespread high-speed internet access, enabling employees in different regions to engage in remote work. Data security and privacy regulations, such as the GDPR, are crucial for maintaining trust and security in remote work environments, ensuring that remote working technologies are used securely. The pandemic has further accelerated the development of policies that provide guidelines for safe and efficient remote work, enhancing the feasibility of remotable jobs. (JRC, 2020a)

4.7.2. Inequalities

The reports also address inequalities. One significant issue is income inequality, which may worsen without counteracting policies (OECD, 2022). Gender wage inequality could increase due to a positive remote working wage premium that systematically benefits men more than women (OECD, 2023). The *OECD Employment Outlook 2022* also notes that RWA currently disproportionately favours highly educated, high-paid, older male employees (OECD, 2022). However, RWA also supports female workers by improving their work-life balance (OECD, 2017).

Additionally, the accessibility to RWA is largely contingent on job position and digital skills (Eurofound, 2022). Addressing this gap might require expanded ICT training for both management and staff (Eurofound & ILO, 2017; OECD, 2021b). The importance of governmental promotion of RWA through facilitating best practice exchanges is underscored by OECD (2017) and Eurofound (2022). Upgrades to digital infrastructures are also seen as crucial (OECD, 2020).

The analysis further uncovers gender disparities. Women are more likely to be in remotable occupations than men, largely due to sectoral employment patterns where women dominate in administrative, clerical, and knowledge-based sectors. However, pre-pandemic data showed minimal gender differences in actual remote work uptake, indicating that women faced barriers in accessing remote work opportunities even when their roles were technically remotable. Regarding age, young people (aged 25–34) are the most likely to have remotable jobs, followed by middle-aged workers (35–54) and then older workers (55–64). However, in more advanced economies, middle-aged individuals are the most likely to have remotable jobs, with no clear pattern for younger and older workers. (EBRD, 2021; JRC, 2020a.)

Income is a decisive factor in teleworkability as well. Higher-income workers are more likely to be in remotable jobs, often holding positions that involve greater autonomy and digital engagement, with less need for physical interaction. This trend highlights a potential exacerbation of income inequality, as those in higher-paying jobs could seamlessly transition to remote work, while lower-income workers faced job insecurity and reduced hours during the pandemic. (EBRD, 2021; Eurofound, 2022; JRC, 2020a.)

Education is another critical factor affecting teleworkability. Workers with tertiary education have a significantly higher likelihood of holding remotable jobs compared to those with lower educational attainment. In fact, tertiary-educated workers are three times more likely to be in roles that can be performed remotely, reflecting the skill set required for remotable occupations. (EBRD, 2021; JRC, 2020a.)

Furthermore, low-skilled, low-income, and part-time workers face significant challenges in remote work. These groups are more likely to be in occupations that require physical presence and manual tasks, making remote work infeasible. This disparity exacerbates their vulnerability to job losses and economic instability during crises like the COVID-19 pandemic. (EBRD, 2021; JRC, 2020a.)

Based on the previous findings, it is evident that there are significant disparities across various socio-economic dimensions. Teleworkability is closely linked to factors such as income, education, gender, and regional differences, which collectively shape the ability of different groups to perform their jobs remotely. The reports highlight the vulnerabilities of low-skilled, low-income, and part-time workers. These groups have the least teleworkability, making them more susceptible to the negative impacts of the pandemic. Their inability to transition to remote work led to higher rates of job losses, furloughs, and reduced working hours, exacerbating existing socio-economic disparities.

5. Spatial and environmental impacts of RWA

The spatial and environmental impacts of RWA have implications to cities and rural areas. They are related to daily activities, travel behaviour, emissions, willingness to relocate residences and workplaces, spatial segregation, and social inequality.

Remote work typically leads to a reduction in daily commuting to work, which might be associated with fewer cars on the roads during peak hours and decreased pressure on public transportation systems, and ultimately with a reduction in emissions. Remote work can improve individual health by reducing exposure to air pollution associated with commuting, and from an environmental perspective, it can lead to significant reductions in greenhouse gas emissions due to decreased traffic.

When there is less need to be near an office and thus greater flexibility in choosing where to live, it can lead to a redistribution of the population from dense urban centres to suburban locations or even smaller municipalities or rural areas. Offices may also downsize or relocate to less expensive areas. On a personal level, the reduced need for commuting allows for more time to engage in family activities, hobbies, or other personal pursuits, thereby improving work-life balance.

However, the ability to work remotely may exacerbate existing segregation and social inequality. Higher-income people who can work remotely may choose to work from their second homes or summer cottages or move to more desirable neighbourhoods. Those in lower-paid or less flexible jobs may not have the option to work remotely, which potentially reinforces socio-economic divides within and between regions.

5.1. Activity and travel behaviour

5.1.1. Impact of RWA for travel behaviour

Impacts of RWA on travel behaviour can be grouped into three broad categories: those focusing on the pre-COVID era, those focusing on the post-COVID era, and those examining impacts with modelling and forecasting.

Travel behaviour before COVID-19

Before COVID-19, research on the impact of RWA on travel behaviour was primarily conducted from the employee's perspective, with an emphasis on WFH and, to a lesser extent, WFS setups like coworking spaces (Bieser et al., 2021; Souche-Le Corvec, 2023). Some others, such as Wöhner (2022, 2023), considered both WFH and WFA.

The findings indicate that RWAs, including WFH and WFA, generally promote leisure-related walking and cycling among remote workers and support active commuting

(Wöhner, 2023). However, the transportation mode to coworking spaces varies, with urban areas favouring non-motorized modes due to better public transport and bicycle infrastructure, whereas suburban and rural areas exhibit higher car usage due to limited alternatives (Souche-Le Corvec, 2023). Remote working notably reduces travel time, particularly when workplace facilities are nearby, encouraging more walking and biking (Bieser et al., 2021).

Despite these benefits, WFH can lead to increased car usage for personal errands and does not significantly reduce overall travel or peak-hour traffic congestion (Long & Reuschke, 2021; Hernandez-Tamurejo et al., 2023). Remote workers often face longer commuting distances and, while they may commute less frequently, their total weekly travel distance can increase, particularly on days they do commute, mainly using public transport (Gubins et al., 2019; Ravalet & Rérat, 2019).

The pre-pandemic era also highlighted several inequalities in RWA impacts. Gender disparities are evident, with women working from home making fewer and shorter trips compared to men, who often have longer commutes (Long & Reuschke, 2021; Ravalet & Rérat, 2019). Flexible work arrangements can reinforce traditional gender roles, particularly affecting women with children who often undertake more domestic tasks (Viana Cerqueira & Motte-Baumvol, 2022). Age and income also influence remote work patterns; older individuals (aged 45–64) and higher-income earners are more likely to work from home, with the latter having greater flexibility in transport choices (Caulfield, 2015; Souche-Le Corvec, 2023). Educational levels correlate with the usage of coworking spaces and remote work frequency, particularly among the self-employed (de Abreu e Silva & Melo, 2018; Souche-Le Corvec, 2023). However, many studies overlook the inequalities faced by vulnerable groups, such as those with restricted mobility or older adults.

Travel behaviour during and after COVID-19

Studies on RWA and travel behaviour during and after COVID-19 primarily focus on employee perspectives, particularly on WFH practices. The research reveals that the pandemic influenced various aspects of RWA, including changes in remote work options, car ownership decisions, and usage of shared mobility services. Additionally, the pandemic affected business travel, lifestyle changes across different life domains, and future commuting plans. The structural increase in RWA post-pandemic has also impacted trip frequency, distance, duration, mode, and environmental outcomes, as well as influenced attitudes towards sustainable mobility and future travel intentions.

Relationships between increased RWA due to the pandemic and reduced overall mobility were found, particularly in urban areas and areas with concentrated financial sectors (Al-Akioui & Monzon, 2023; Campisi et al., 2022), and these findings are consistent both before and during the pandemic (Faber et al., 2023a) though RWA transitions were more drastic for those starting during the pandemic compared to those already with RWA (Reiffer et al., 2023). These changes are particularly evident

during morning peak hours and for rail- and car-users who shifted to RWA during the pandemic (Magriço et al., 2023; Faber et al., 2023b; Ton et al., 2022), highlighting the impact on commuting behaviour specifically (Ecke et al., 2022), with initial trends in returning to regular behaviour after the pandemic slowest among those previously using public transport (de Séjournet et al., 2022; Magriço et al., 2023). Some studies saw minor increases in car and public transport use during the pandemic, though insignificant compared to those shifting to RWA, indicating that those continuing to work or study in person may have taken advantage of decreased traffic and congestion (Hook et al., 2020; Shakibael et al., 2021). It should be noted that reduction in commuting frequency and business trips found due to the pandemic is largely influenced by the employer's decisions rather than individual motivations to act in a climate-aware manner (Wilke et al., 2022), though nonetheless positively impacting the environment in the short term (Crowley et al., 2021), and the closure of retail establishments more heavily impact non-cycling modes (de Séjournet et al., 2022). On the other hand, an increase in RWA is associated with increased (or at least maintained) walking and cycling following reduced commuting needs and increased leisure time (Campisi et al., 2022; de Séjournet et al., 2022; Faber et al., 2023a; Hook et al., 2020), with supporters of RWA found to be 4.2 times more likely to increase their cycling frequency than their neutral counterparts (Campisi et al., 2020).

Structural increases in RWA due to the pandemic may result in desirable effects with travel patterns more dispersed throughout the day, potentially reducing congestion (Faber et al., 2023b), or by promoting sustainable mobility in suburban areas, potentially reducing the need for car commuting (Krasilnikova & Levin-Keitel, 2022). However, while car use may have decreased for those with both part and full time RWA (Vega-Gonzalo et al., 2023b), a return to pre-pandemic driving levels is eventually seen (de Séjournet et al., 2022). Further, car ownership did not decrease during the pandemic, and in fact there was heightened car purchases among those with full- or part-time RWA, those who previously owned cars, and those who increased their use of shared mobility, though not among those with higher accessibility to public transport (Vega-Gonzalo et al., 2023a).

On the other hand, after the initial pandemic regulations, RWA are not found to consistently reduce travel. In many cases, those with RWA travel farther, including for non-work purposes, and there is increased business travel among those with RWA (Caldarola & Sorrell, 2022) with no substantial effects on mode choice reported when it comes to commute and business trips (Faber et al., 2023b). Overall, RWA affect public transport commute travel time more than travel time for the other modes (Faber et al., 2023a) and it is estimated that an increase in RWA could lead to a 1-3% decrease in annual CO₂ emissions in the transport sector if adopted widely (Crowley et al., 2021). Further, no significant impacts of RWA are found on locational decisions (Faber et al., 2023b).

In terms of equity, studies exploring the impacts of RWA on travel behaviour during and after the COVID-19 pandemic reveal a number of discrepancies with more than half of the studies touching on this topic. First, job functions of many workers (up to

53% in one study; see Crowley et al., 2021) during this time did not support RWA, particularly those with lower income and education levels, who continued to commute and did not change their commuting times or modes significantly (Ecke et al., 2022). On the other hand, travel behaviour is similarly affected regardless of residential neighbourhood, though suburban residents are found to have more mode-resilience and less public transport-reliance (Hook et al., 2020). The benefits of RWA are found to be restricted to privileged socio-economic groups with a greater likelihood of entering into flexible RWA (Hook et al., 2020; Vega-Gonzalo et al., 2023b), therefore though RWA are often regarded as a policy tool to reduce car use for urban trips, this scope and its benefits may be limited.

Modelling, forecasting, and simulation

The simulation studies reviewed explore the impacts of RWA on travel behaviour and related emissions, employing various modelling and forecasting techniques. Some of these studies also consider the role of employers in shaping these outcomes (Stermieri et al., 2023; Moeckel 2017a; Alonso et al., 2017).

Moeckel (2017a) introduces a simulation framework that integrates a microscopic transport simulation model with a land use model to estimate the effects of remote work on travel behaviour and land use. This framework accounts for factors like social networks, smartphone and GPS device ownership, and e-commerce usage. A subsequent paper by Moeckel (2017b) extends this model to explore the combined effects of remote work and home relocation.

Alonso et al. (2017) apply the Metropolitan Activity Relocation Model, a macro strategic Land Use Transport Interaction model, to the Madrid region to simulate the impacts of various measures including remote working, over a 30-year period. Their findings suggest that while measures like re-densification reduce travel distances, remote working increases total energy consumption due to heightened non-commuting mobility, despite reducing commuting times and congestion.

Stermieri et al. (2023) contrast two scenarios differing in ICT adoption levels. They find that while remote working reduces energy demand in tertiary sectors and transport in the high ICT adoption scenario, it increases residential energy demand, thus neutralizing overall energy savings. The study emphasizes the need for technological investments and building renovations to harness the full benefits of remote work.

Kiko et al. (2024) examine the direct and rebound effects of remote working in the Paris region using a standard four-step transport model across 25 scenarios. They report significant initial reductions in travel due to remote working, which are substantially diminished when accounting for rebound effects such as induced demand and changes in residential locations. Despite these reductions, the social benefits of remote working remain substantial.

Lastly, Stefaniec et al. (2024) investigate the combined impact of remote working and road transport electrification using a four-step transport model. Their scenarios show that moderate to high levels of remote working significantly reduce the number of trips and emissions, although a high private car mode share persists.

Overall, these studies highlight the complex interplay between remote working, travel behaviour, and environmental impacts, underscoring the importance of complementary policies and technological advancements to optimize the benefits of remote work arrangements.

5.1.2. Impact of RWA for daily activities

Research examining the impacts of RWA on daily activities and routines, primarily conducted post-2020, explores various dimensions of everyday life impacted by remote work, with particular attention to WFH (Puspita et al., 2023; Ciriaco et al., 2023; Nguyen et al., 2021; Hensher et al., 2023). Researchers examine the experiences and viewpoints mainly of employees, sometimes comparing remote workers' experiences with those who do not work remotely (Khaddar et al., 2023), while most studies consider the broader perspective of the general population (Ciriaco et al., 2023; Shah et al., 2024).

One of the most significant findings is the remarkable increase in online activities (Mouratidis & Peters, 2022; Mouratidis & Papagiannakis, 2021). RWA have made online shopping more accessible, resulting in a shift from traditional in-person shopping to e-shopping (Ciriaco et al., 2023; Shah et al., 2024). This shift includes a marked rise in online grocery shopping, particularly during the COVID-19 lockdown period, when the adoption of e-shopping and home delivery services surged (Matson et al., 2023). Remote working is positively correlated with more frequent e-purchasing for electronics (Nguyen et al., 2021). Moreover, individuals with a pro-remote-work attitude tend to view online shopping favourably, driven by the belief that ICT applications enhance quality of life (Asgari et al., 2023).

Another significant finding is the change in activity engagement and time allocation. Remote workers, with their more flexible schedules, engage in activities differently compared to non-remote workers (Khaddar et al., 2023). Overall, they spend more time on in-home activities (Losa Rovira et al., 2022). They tend to allocate more time to breaks, leisure activities, and household responsibilities during the workday (Khaddar et al., 2023). Additionally, remote workers are more likely to engage in discretionary activities such as leisure and social activities (Balbontin et al., 2024; Loo & Wang, 2018) and travel less for routine tasks like shopping and healthcare (Bhuiyan & Habib, 2024).

These changes in daily activity patterns, more than just temporary responses to the pandemic, have the potential to become established behaviours with long-term effects (Matson et al., 2023; Khaddar et al., 2023). The effects of RWA on online, in-home, and discretionary activities underscore the importance of considering these evolving

preferences in future spatial and transport planning strategies. As residential areas become multifunctional hubs for work, leisure, and daily activities (Puspita et al., 2023), higher spatial fragmentation patterns are also observed among those with a higher willingness to e-work (Arranz-López & Soria-Lara, 2022). The involvement of cyberspace, facilitated by online activities, becomes an integral part of spatial planning efforts, emphasizing the need for a holistic approach to land use and activity integration (Puspita et al., 2023). Accessible, mixed-use areas could enable remote workers to engage in more sustainable non-work activities, highlighting the importance of considering the broader context in which remote working occurs (Budnitz et al., 2020; Hensher et al., 2023).

The literature also highlights some differences and inequalities when exploring the effects of RWA on daily activities, particularly in terms of gender and age. Female remote workers tend to focus more on household-related responsibilities (e.g., shopping), while female non-remote workers tend to prioritize personal business-related activities (Khaddat et al., 2023). Additionally, senior workers are found to face challenges when working remotely, particularly in adapting to online activities (Dianat et al., 2022).

5.2. Location decisions

5.2.1. Employees' willingness to relocate residences

Remote work is widely considered to be a way to solve mobility issues by reducing the need to travel to the office and therefore decreasing the number of commuting trips. However, Section 5.1.1 already indicated that there may be rebound effects: employees may indeed save the trip to work, but often replace it with trips for other purposes. However, this is not the only possible rebound effect of remote work. When employees have, for example, the possibility to work from home frequently, it eliminates the need to live close to work. This may prompt employees to reconsider their residential location choice and live further away from their conventional workplace, which might exacerbate urban sprawl. However, despite frequently working from home, these remote workers still must commute to the workplace from time to time. In this way, working from home may on one hand reduce the number of daily commuting trips, but it might increase the distance travelled over a working week.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, several studies reported how people moved away from urban areas and that this was partly due to the increase in WFH (e.g., Al-Akioui & Monzon, 2023; Paköz & Kaya (2023)). Findings like this create the impression that WFH indeed results in residential relocations away from urban areas. However, this “urban exodus” needs to be nuanced. First, although there might be signs that employees move further away from their workplace, they often remain in the same metropolitan region as before (Paköz & Kaya, 2023). This is partly because employers are aware that WFH may encourage their employees to relocate but at the same time ask them to

stay within a reasonable commuting distance to the conventional workplace (Šmite et al., 2023). Second, relocations were studied against a context during the pandemic with a variety of safety measures of which WFH was just one. Relocations often appeared to be driven by a need for extra space, including extra workspace because of the increase in WFH, but equally important access to a garden or proximity to nature (Thulin et al., 2023; Wolday & Böcker, 2023). Moreover, residential satisfaction and residential attachment might be important mediators in the link between WFH and the intention to relocate (Van Acker et al., 2024).

Based on these insights about WFH and residential relocations during the COVID-19 pandemic, simulation studies like Moser et al. (2022) for Munich suggested that the reduced need for commuting due to WFH may lead to an “outward relocation” trend, i.e., away from central urban areas, even post pandemic. However, they also observed a gradual yet discontinuous decay from the core of Munich city to the fringes as the number of days working from home increases. This suggests a spatial preference towards specific areas in the region, mainly secondary cities offering urban qualities while being more affordable compared to the main city of Munich, as well as locations easily accessible by public transport as employees want to stay in acceptable commuting distance from the conventional workplace.

While these studies assume that WFH has an impact on residential location choice, there are also a number of studies that study the opposite relationship, namely how the decision to WFH is influenced by where one lives. Several studies have found that the willingness to WFH is indeed higher among those who already live further away from their workplace and have longer commuting distances or times (Stefaniec et al., 2022; Paköz & Kaya, 2023; Šmite et al., 2023). De Vos et al. (2018) found even before the COVID-19 pandemic that WFH was associated with 5% longer commutes on average.

5.2.2. Employees’ willingness to relocate workplaces

In addition to reconsidering their residential choice, employees may also start reconsidering their job choice and with it also the location of their conventional workplace. For example, for several employees, working from home during the pandemic was a positive experience. If their employer wants the workforce back in the office and therefore starts restricting remote work, this may lead some employees to quit their job and start looking for a job with more flexibility regarding remote work (Šmite et al., 2023). This new job with greater remote work flexibility may be located further away from home compared to the former job. Remote work could thus allow employees to tap into a larger pool of jobs.

However, if that is the case, it also again causes increasing commuting distances as employees will still have to commute to their workplace now and then, creating another rebound effect of remote work. To the best of our knowledge, there are no studies on employees’ willingness to change jobs and possibly accepting a job offer from an employer located further away to enjoy more remote work flexibility. The only

studies on employees' workplace location choices we could find are related to the employees' decisions to work from home versus to go work at the office (Asmussen et al., 2023; Cañibano, 2019; van Zoonen et al., 2021), but all of these are related to the current job.

Most of these studies consider a binary workplace location choice, i.e., working from home versus going to the office. Only Asmussen et al. (2023) also considered a third option: alternative work locations such as co-working locations, hotels, or restaurants. They found differences between the three types of workplace locations which also reveal important inequalities. WFH is preferred by those with long commutes and high traffic congestion to the conventional work office, which again points to the question of causality between WFH and residential location choices as mentioned. It is also preferred by individuals with a private study in their homes, self-employed workers, those in non-essential service occupations and single young women with very young children, the latter possibly indicating a form of inequality with women once again taking on the biggest share of caring responsibilities. Working at the conventional work office is preferred by older men, individuals from low-income households, those residing in rural areas and workers in essential service occupations. The third workplace location seems to be preferred by non-single young women with very young children, individuals from low-income households, part-time employees, and those in professional, managerial or finance occupations.

5.2.3. Employers' willingness to downsize and/or relocate offices

Not only employees may reconsider their home and work location choices, but employers can also reconsider the location of their company when their employees no longer have to be present in the office en masse at the same time. They could decide to stay in the same location but downsize the office space, or they may even decide to move to a cheaper location.

There was some attention to the potential impact of RWA on companies downsizing floor space even before the COVID-19 pandemic. However, it was often based on assumptions without actually surveying employers. Since the pandemic, this research field has gained new momentum (Barath & Schmidt, 2022; Ring, 2022; Hensher et al., 2023; Oladiran et al., 2023; Riahi Samani et al., 2024; Satariano & Bajada, 2023). Still, it mainly focuses on how remote work can lead to companies downsizing their floor space rather than reconsidering their locations.

In one of the few studies that focus on business relocations, Riahi Samani et al. (2024) found that before the pandemic, business relocation decisions were mainly influenced by company characteristics such as size, value, age, and type. However, the importance of these characteristics was reduced by half after the pandemic. Instead, the nature of the office space and accessibility became much more influential. Although accessibility is now one of the most important factors determining business

relocation decisions, its relative importance has somewhat declined. This may indicate that due to more remote work after the pandemic, companies now look differently at the accessibility of their business site since employees do not have to come to the office as frequently as before. However, Riahi Samani et al. (2024) were unable to include data on remote work directly in their model, and thus the effect of remote work on company relocation decisions remains hypothetical.

The changing role of accessibility, and especially physical proximity, is confirmed by Ring (2022). In their study, most employers indicated that they would adjust the size of their office spaces in the future. Since their employees are no longer going to be all present together at the same time at the office, it is necessary to prepare the company for moments of what Ring (2022) calls “thickness” – several employees at the office when meetings and social interaction is needed – and “thinness” – when employees work remotely and are not present at the office. This involves no longer providing single occupied office spaces but relying more on open workspaces and flexible workstations. Similarly, Barath and Schmidt (2022) postulate that remote work will not result in an office exodus, but rather in how existing offices are used.

Along with a different, more flexible use of office space, there also seems to be consensus on how remote work will lead to a downsizing of office space, albeit this is based on a limited number of studies on this topic. Oladiran et al. (2023) found that companies with a positive remote work experience during the pandemic are more likely to reduce their total space quantity and occupation density in the near future. Hensher et al. (2023) go one step further and study how remote work is not only linked to changes in the utilization of the workspace at the main office, but also how this correlates with changes in demand for satellite offices. Assuming the most likely scenario of one to two days of WFH per week for most employees, their model predicts a 20–28 per cent reduction in office space compared to pre-COVID-19.

5.3. Environmental impacts

5.3.1. Physical activity

Most studies examining the impact of remote work on physical activity have focused on the period during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. However, two notable exceptions that used pre-COVID data are Budnitz et al. (2020) and Wöhner (2023). Budnitz et al. (2020) suggest that trip-making budgets are similar for remote workers and non-remote workers, indicating that commuting trips not made by remote workers are often reallocated to other purposes. They also note that for these other trips to increase physical activity through walking or cycling, the neighbourhoods should be walkable and feature dispersed points of interest that provide basic services and amenities. Conversely, Wöhner (2023) found that remote workers tend to walk and cycle more for discretionary purposes than those who work in an office, although the overall likelihood of using active modes of transportation is not influenced by their

working arrangement. Additionally, flextime is associated with a higher frequency of walking. Wöhner (2023) also notes that less active travel is associated with full-time work, car ownership, and a higher body mass index.

Recent studies conducted during and after the COVID-19 pandemic have generally found that the introduction of remote work influenced lifestyles and physical activity behaviours, typically resulting in reduced physical activity while working from home (Argus and Pääsuke, 2021; Brusaca et al., 2022; Fiorini, 2023; Keightley et al., 2023; Sers et al., 2023; Widar et al., 2021). However, some subgroups experienced an increase in physical activity levels. Notably, the study by Franco et al. (2021) observed a significant increase in total physical activity during the pandemic compared to before. It is important to note that the participants in this study were enrolled in a health promotion program, which may have influenced the results, leading to higher levels of both sedentarism and physical activity during the pandemic, as these are not mutually exclusive.

Keightley et al. (2023) conducted semi-structured interviews in the UK during full-time working at home, and the results indicated that physical activity was reduced during lockdown periods, although some participants engaged in purposeful activities before and/or after working hours to compensate for lower physical activity. Other researchers found that Spanish women's physical health decreased due to worse work-family balance (Loezar-Hernández et al., 2023); and Swedish tech employees that gained extra weight due to inactivity (Šmite et al., 2023), while complaining about the blurred boundary between work and private life. Interestingly, some of their respondents also declared an improved work-life balance as family time increased (Šmite et al., 2023). Similar results were found in Malta, with few participants reporting having a less hectic life and calmer work environments as benefits of working remotely (Fiorini, 2023).

Buffey et al. (2023) proposed using passive prompt interventions to increase physical activity while working from home. Their results indicate a reduction on the prolonged sedentary bouts, and increased light-intensity physical activity; proving that these interventions can compensate for reduced physical activity while commuting. Also, it is significant the proportion of work tasks via remote working: Fiorini (2023) found that those who were carrying all tasks remotely had less negative change during the lockdown than those with a smaller proportion of remote tasks.

On the other hand, the results in Sweden found that physical behaviours did not change significantly based on the accelerometer measurements (Hallman et al., 2021); and that only minor differences are found between working days from home and at the office (Brusaca et al., 2022), with more sedentary time in short and long bouts, and slightly reduced physical activity. The results are similar in Germany (Sers et al., 2023), with less physical activity intensity on the days working from home compared to the days at the office, which was reflected as well in fewer steps and less moderate physical activity. Interestingly, they found more short physical activity bouts, as in the results from Swedish academics (Widar et al., 2021).

For leisure activities, Kantyka and Maciąg (2024) found an increase in occasional exercise frequency and a decrease on the number of workouts for individuals who worked out between 3 and 4 times per week in Poland. The results in Germany, on the other hand, found that recreational activities increased but also sedentary time (Herbolsheimer et al., 2024). Argus and Pääsuke (2021) also reported lower sport index.

5.3.2. Emissions

Studies analysing environmental impacts often take a similar approach to the studies listed in the Section 5.1.1 by modelling mode split and travel distances under various scenarios of remote work, then going a step further by estimating associated greenhouse gas emissions from increased or decreased energy impacts, and in some cases, other pollutants. Most papers have chosen to analyse various real or hypothetical scenarios which are then run through a transport model to generate modelled impacts, with two studies applying an agent-based model (Hofer et al., 2018; Tenailleau et al., 2021).

Although the COVID-19 pandemic is often mentioned as a justification for exploring the impacts of remote work, only three out of the fourteen energy-related studies explicitly studied a COVID-19 period as one of the comparative scenarios (Beno, 2021; Ceccato et al., 2022; Kareinen et al., 2022). One study included data collection from both employees and employers (Roberto et al., 2023), but like all other studies, the analysis was limited to remote workers. Most studies examined only WFH arrangements, with only one explicitly expanding its definition of RWA to also include WFA (Tenailleau et al., 2021) and another focussing on co-working spaces as a special case of WFS (Ohnmacht et al., 2020).

In terms of potential for greenhouse gas emission reductions, results intriguingly differ quite substantially between studies. The main reason, aside from differences in study areas, methodologies, and data sources, is the scope of what effects were included in each study and the scenarios used to compare with the baseline scenario. It is therefore necessary to categorise the range of possible impacts to account for, and to analyse the scenarios used. As a starting reference, Kiko et al. (2024) suggested to break effects down between direct (commuting effects) and indirect (rebound) effects. Labidurie Omnes et al. (2023) extends this framework by distinguishing between first order, second order, and higher order effects for the use of ICT as a key enabler for RWA. The possible effects of first order effects, which relate to technical infrastructure, are additional device manufacturing to enable RWA (e.g., screens and laptops), and increased use of ICT solutions and their energy impacts.

The second order effects consist of travel-related and energy related effects, such as changes in emissions from commuting and changes in transport modes used. These are called direct effects in Kiko et al. (2024) and are the most-often considered effects in all studies. In addition, second order effects also include changes in non-work travel,

everyday activities and mobility, changes in energy consumption at home, changes in energy consumption at work premises, and impacts from using a co-working space.

The higher order (rebound) effects consist of home relocation effects (e.g., an employee moving further away from their office), reuse of a vehicle by other family members, working from other locations than home, and so-called induced demand: A rebound effect from reducing traffic during peak hours, which increases capacity, which reduces travel times (and therefore travel costs) for the remaining population, therefore attracting additional traffic.

In summary, most studies conclude on a significant potential reduction of greenhouse gas emissions related to the direct effect of reduced distances travelled to work, but net emission reductions depend on whether remote work takes place in urban or rural areas, and whether previously commuted distances were done by public transport (low-carbon modes) or car (high carbon modes). Studies which considered non-work trips show that the commuting gains are offset by additional local trips, especially if done by car or if additional activities are carbon intensive. Remote working can only reduce overall energy consumption under certain conditions, particularly if the office space that was previously used is reduced or closed. The impacts from additional ICT use are marginal. Most studies do not consider home relocation effects, far-away remote working, reuse of the family vehicle by other members, or induced demand from road capacity freed by remote working.

In terms of inequalities, studies that have compiled gender data agree that men and higher income workers tend to have higher carbon footprints (Cerqueira et al., 2020; Roberto et al., 2023), with generally a higher percentage of men working remotely (O'Keefe et al., 2016) but with women being more willing to adopt remote work for more days than men (Ceccato et al., 2022).

5.4. Socio-spatial impacts

5.4.1. Socio-spatial inequality due to RWA

The increasing prevalence of RWA allows employees and their households greater flexibility in choosing their place of residence (see Section 5.2.1) and reevaluating their remote work locations (see Section 5.2.2). From a societal viewpoint, this influences settlement patterns and affects both urban and regional development. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, studies on travel behaviour linked WFH with longer commuting distances (de Vos et al., 2018), thereby contributing to urban sprawl. Since 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic has induced a significant (temporary) shift towards remote working, which has also generated inequalities among individuals regarding the opportunity to work remotely, depending on job nature (Li & Wei, 2023). While the adoption of RWA is contingent on the teleworkability of a job, which varies across employer sectors (see Section 4.7.1) and countries (Luca et al., 2024), it raises questions

about the societal impacts of RWA from a spatial perspective – specifically, how RWA contributes to spatial segregation and social inequality in the long term.

Studies from the COVID-19 pandemic show how the spatial segregation increased between socioeconomic and ethnic groups regarding their daily use of urban space (Müürisepp et al., 2023) as well as people with access to second homes fled from larger cities to stay in less dense rural areas (Willberg et al., 2021). However, studies showing the increase of spatial segregation and social inequality due to the COVID-19 pandemic do not explicitly examine the impact of RWA. Our review using a broad keyword search on RWA and socio-spatial inequality yielded 128 articles, while only six articles were empirically studying these two aspects – two studies from USA, three from Europe and one global study. This clearly indicates how little attention has been put on the impact of RWA on society from a spatial segregation and social inequality perspective to date. All five empirical articles are published since 2021, which indicates the aspect becoming significant after the COVID-19 disruption.

A non-empirical critical commentary by Florida et al. (2023) predicts that there is minor long-term impact of RWA on urban fabric and settlement structure arguing that people with high RWA potentially still want urban amenities and opportunities in attractive metropolitan cities. They further predict that in case dense urban centres do lose population, then people will relocate to nearby suburbs and small towns, and medium-sized cities and remote rural areas continue to lose economic attractiveness and people.

These predictions are confirmed by two empirical studies at regional and global scale. Study by Braesemann et al. (2022) focusing specifically on digital online platform workers at global scale found remote jobs concentrating more towards larger cities and rural regions to be less attractive. Thus, suggesting existing concentration of human capital, information and communication technologies and urban opportunities to pull more remote work and further increase spatial inequality between regions (metropolitan vs rural) and between countries (developed vs developing countries). Similarly, Irlacher and Koch (2021) argue remote work concentrating more to existing urban centres of opportunities, skills and capital and thus having stronger pull effect than price differentials to attract remote work to regions with lower living costs. Claims were based on a study on employees in Germany finding a clear positive relation between WFH and average income level, at regional level. Regions in the eastern part of Germany tend to underperform and thus indicating RWA to increase urban-rural imbalances within countries. These studies rely on data before 2020.

In contrast, a study during the pandemic by Howard et al. (2023) examined the short- and long-run effects of remote work on U.S. housing markets affected regional differences. Their modelling predictions based on housing supply and rental prices suggest that people moved to more rural areas where housing costs were lower due to RWA opportunities, and not only due to temporary pandemic related factors from a shorter perspective. In the long-run, their predictions indicate that with RWA

opportunities increasing, people move away from high-density and high price areas (like city centres) and most expensive metropolitan areas and towards lower-density, lower price areas, such as suburbs and rural areas. Similarly, a study by Åberg et al (2021) conducted during COVID-19 in a rural region in Sweden argues that the pandemic increased an interest in green spaces and rural living, in general, and that the main motivations for relocation were the quality of life and existing second home in countryside. While permanent and temporary in-migration to rural areas is seen primarily positive development by local people, it can cause inequality among local community – local (younger) people cannot afford increased property prices due to in-migration and are forced to move away to nearby cities with more affordable housing.

Burchell et al. (2021) focusing on urban employees in the 28 European countries showed gender inequality regarding the location of work – women are more restricted to only work at the employer’s premises (69%) compared to men (46%). Potential to work elsewhere means foremostly for women working from home, whereas men having more diverse and complex spatiotemporal patterns for work locations. Study also found a clear difference between regions – the Scandinavian countries are markedly more flexible with (remote) working locations than other countries in Europe.

However, none of the studies focused strictly on how residential relocation due to RWA affects spatial inequality regarding population composition at neighbourhood and city level. Certainly, similarly to Howard et al. (2023), economists have properly started to estimate the impact of RWA on housing and real-estate property and rental markets since the COVID-19 pandemic (e.g. Althoff et al., 2022; Ramani and Bloom, 2022; Haslag and Weagley, 2023), yet their focus is on economic aspects and not on social implications on urban fabric and spatial inequalities.

5.5. Specific case studies

5.5.1. Cross-border mobility

The impact of RWA on travel behaviour of employees is ambiguous to begin with (see Section 5.1.1), but when this is studied in a cross-border region, it is potentially even more complex. Differences in taxation and social security make it for cross-border workers not always that easy to WFH as frequently as local residents (see Section 4.6.1). From this point of view, one might expect the impact of WFH on commuting and daily mobility to be less strong for cross-border workers compared to local residents. However, to the best of our knowledge, we could not find any study on the differential impact of WFH for residents and cross-border workers.

Moreover, to attract and retain cross-border workers, companies in cross-border regions like Luxembourg are setting up a network of satellite offices near the borders (Klein, 2023). Instead of commuting the longer distance to the main office, cross-border workers can still save some time by commuting the usually shorter distance to

the satellite office instead. In doing so, satellite offices offer thus some flexibility to cross-border workers in terms of work location choices while avoiding problems related to taxation and social security linked to frequent WFH. Companies in cross-border regions thus seem to be experimenting with different types of RWA (not only WFH, but also WFS). But again, we could not find any study that elaborates on the possible mobility impacts of such satellite offices in a border region like Luxembourg.

5.5.2. Digital nomadism and gentrification

Digital nomads can have a significant impact on the cities they live in, both positively and negatively. One of the main possible negative impacts is gentrification, which occurs when a change in the socio-economic composition of a neighbourhood leads to an increase in living costs (mostly housing prices and rents) and changes in the commercial structure (traditional shops replaced by specialized shops catering the needs of the new residents) and the expulsion of the previous residents and consequential change in the neighbourhood social structure. Because the income of the digital nomads is not dependent on the local economy characteristics, they can influence housing prices and create a demand for specific types of commerce of which the local population can be excluded due to their lower purchase power.

As Bozzi (2020) states:

“Discussing financial status and the gig economy, Thompson (2018) outlines a clear imbalance between the cultural capital of digital nomads, who are mostly well-educated English speakers with strong passports, and their professional options (p. 12). There is also an imbalance between their home countries, where living standards are declining, and the affordable destinations where digital nomads travel to – which, as a consequence – are subject to increased gentrification (p. 3).”

Of the 15 articles that we reviewed, only two focus on the pre-pandemic period and three focus specifically on the pandemic years. Chevtaeva and Denizci-Guillet (2021) discuss the possible impacts of the pandemic on the phenomenon of digital nomads. They state that having office in a more exotic place makes sense, especially during the emotional distress of COVID-19 in big and crowded cities. They further predict that digital nomadism as a movement is expected to grow after the pandemic, and the understanding of digital nomads should be more theoretically informed and go beyond grounded in the complexities of local context studies.

Some of the more recent empirical studies focus not only on the current situation at the time of the study but also speculate about future scenarios. Biagetti et al. (2024) discovered that remote workers and digital nomads could induce different scenarios of migration from the main cities to smaller urban areas and more suburban settings. These different scenarios could lead to different gentrification/housing prices outcomes, either maintaining current high house prices in central areas, with low

migration to the periphery or larger migration to peripheral/suburban areas, with negative impacts in the city centre (that could in an extreme situation lead to a “donut” configuration) while at the same time increasing real estate prices in less urban areas.

It was noted by Biagetti et al. (2024) that there are differences between the genders that impact migration scenarios differently. The authors describe that women are more likely to choose residences that are closer to nature and value proximity to the workplace less. One of the motivations for this trend is that only if women are away from their workplace, they are allowed (by the management) to start working remotely. Of all the studies, this was the only one that pointed out some inequality between the results obtained from different perspectives (e.g., age, gender, income, education); this issue is still poorly explored.

Gil et al. (2023), on the other hand, have made discoveries about the increase in rents and possible changes in the financialization of housing. In general, due to the pandemic, there has been an exponential increase in short-term rentals and, even with the end of the restriction period, several listings have not returned to the conventional real estate market, remaining short-term rentals. As a result, the authors point out that without a stricter public policy protecting the right to housing and the right to live in the city, the future scenario of the “platformization” of housing will result in less stable and less affordable rental prices, increasing the precariousness of housing and impoverishing tenants.

Finally, Jung and Buhr (2022) demonstrate that digital nomads are entangled with urban infrastructures and services that facilitate and enable their lifestyles and the existence of third places in which they can work from. Overall, the future prospect is that the more an immigrant’s business is connected to the mobility network, the more immigrants will be attracted to it.

5.5.3. Multi-locality and second homes

Of the 10 articles that we included in the final review about the impact of multi-locality and second homes on remote work, six were studies within the Finnish context, which emphasizes not only that Finland is a key hub for research on multi-local living and spatial planning but also that second homes and summer houses are part of the Finnish national culture.

Before the pandemic, Ojala and Pyöriä (2018) explored the prevalence of multi-locational work across Europe, noting its popularity in northern European countries due to the high proportion of knowledge-intensive occupations. Despite the technological advancements that facilitate remote work, they found that most knowledge workers still worked from their employers' premises, suggesting a gap between expectations and reality in remote work adoption.

Kojo and Nenonen (2016) provided a typology of coworking spaces in and around Helsinki, categorizing them based on business models and accessibility. They

emphasized the concept of “activity-based workplaces,” which cater to various uses, highlighting the shift towards multi-locality and more dynamic work environments. Di Marino et al. (2018) further investigated how multi-locational work was supported in Helsinki through policy and planning. They discovered a reluctance among policymakers to fully embrace multi-locality, with a continued focus on monofunctional spaces despite a slow shift towards multifunctionality. This was contrasted by organizations that were experimenting with various multi-functional spaces and arrangements, such as equipping employees’ summer cottages with IT infrastructure and creating temporary working hubs around the city. Building on this, Di Marino and Lapintie (2020) studied how individuals utilized public spaces like libraries and cafes for work in Helsinki’s city centre. They concluded that monofunctional spaces no longer represent the emerging socio-spatial practices of urban multi-local workers, so both city design and planning as well as urban service businesses and public spaces must become “post-functional,” meaning that they should provide space for different purposes including work.

Part of the Nordic way of life is proximity to nature, and owning or renting a summer cottage in a rural area is popular in Finland (called *mökki* in Finnish) and Norway (*hytte* in Norwegian). The integration of work into these spaces has been noted by Di Marino et al. (2018, 2023). This trend was particularly pronounced during the COVID-19 pandemic, with increased usage of these spaces for work. In Norway, Di Marino et al. (2023) found that during the pandemic, summer cottages were used for 70–90 days per year (compared to 40–50 days pre-pandemic), indicating that many people preferred to continue working from there.

Some studies propose that multi-local work can contribute to revitalizing small, medium-sized, and rural municipalities. According to Di Marino et al. (2023), coworking spaces can be helpful for smaller cities and rural areas, because they attract those seeking better work-life balance, closer contact with nature, tighter communities, and more outdoor activities than what major cities can provide for them. Similarly, Schmidt-Thome and Lilius (2023) found that a local government in Puolanka, Finland, viewed multi-locality as a potential solution to demographic challenges. Efforts were made to accommodate multi-locals and integrate them into the community, reflecting hopes for leveraging remote work for local development. Kiviaho and Toivonen (2023) discussed the broader implications of remote work and multi-local living for urban shrinkage, suggesting that these trends could offer new opportunities for economic and social revitalization in declining urban areas.

However, Flipo et al. (2022) critically assessed the impact of rural coworking spaces in France. While these spaces aimed to address various territorial challenges, such as enhancing sustainability by reducing the need to commute, tackling the digital gap between city centres and peripheries, and reducing inequalities by safeguarding local jobs and attracting new residents, the authors questioned the long-term demographic and sociological effects, pointing out the transient nature of urbanites’ engagement with rural areas.

According to the findings, multi-locality and remote work from second homes provide many opportunities for rural municipalities that are facing a shrinking and ageing population. However, there are potential problems that need to be addressed in case a growing number of remote workers choose to move to smaller municipalities or stay in their summer cottages for extensive periods of time. These include inadequate health and emergency services, lack of public transport resulting in higher dependency on cars, and an increasing burden on the IT infrastructure which is often not built for heavy use. (Di Marino et al., 2023.) In addition, it is important to consider that urbanites seemingly seeking a “simpler” and slower lifestyle in a rural area closer to nature may wish to do so only on a short-term basis, instead of a lasting change in the attitudes towards rural living (Flipo et al., 2022).

6. Main knowledge gaps

6.1. Gaps in social and cultural impacts of RWA

Mental health and well-being

Our literature review highlights significant knowledge gaps in the study of remote working and mental health, particularly in differentiating the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic from the general impacts of remote work on mental health and well-being. There is a noted need for further research in the post-COVID era to better understand the long-term implications of remote work on aspects such as stress, isolation, and loneliness. Additionally, the perspectives of employers on remote working are underrepresented in existing studies. More research is required to comprehend employers' challenges and strategies, which is vital for developing effective workplace policies and support systems.

Our review also points out the lack of studies that include diverse job roles and hierarchical levels within organizations. Understanding the unique experiences and challenges faced by different job roles can aid in creating targeted interventions. Moreover, most existing studies do not specify the geographical context of their research, overlooking potential differences between urban and rural settings that could affect remote working experiences.

We also identify cultural frameworks, socioeconomic factors, living situations, and educational backgrounds as areas needing more exploration to understand their influence on remote workers' mental health and well-being. Lastly, there is a call for more qualitative research to capture the subjective experiences and perceptions of remote workers, providing deeper insights into the challenges they encounter.

Quality of time

To effectively evaluate the impact of RWA on time-use and the quality of working time, several key areas need exploration. Firstly, it is essential to compare different types of remote work in terms of their temporal characteristics, such as work duration, timing, and sequencing, and assess their effects on both objective (e.g., multitasking, time fragmentation) and subjective (e.g., stress, work-family balance) quality indicators. Secondly, it is crucial to identify and analyse inequalities in time-use quality between remote and non-remote workers, and among different categories of remote workers, considering job and socio-demographic factors. This analysis should also explore whether RWAs contribute to new forms of inequality. Lastly, the potential of full-time RWA to serve as an alternative to part-time employment should be examined, particularly in terms of its capacity to improve work-family alignment and reduce gender disparities in labour division and outcomes.

Daily rhythms and household task arrangements

The literature that we have reviewed corroborates the findings of prior research in daily rhythms and household tasks. However, to gain a deeper understanding of the impact of the RWA on daily rhythms and household task arrangements, further aspects need to be examined. These include the role of family and friends in providing emotional and social support to manage daily life, financial resources, as well as housing characteristics (such as size, layout, and composition). Additionally, the conflict between domestic and professional spheres, especially in scenarios where there is inadequate support for employees from their companies, should be explored.

Policy and regulatory gaps in mental health and well-being

Across EU member states, there are limited regulations specifically aimed at mitigating the negative effects of RWA on mental health. While there are a few exceptions, most countries offer recommendations rather than enforceable regulatory measures. The majority of EU countries do not explicitly address the impacts of RWA on mental health in their policies. When mentioned, it is often only in the context of the “right to disconnect,” the effectiveness of which in ensuring a healthy work-life balance and protecting employees' mental health is challenging to determine. This lack of consideration fails to fully explore both the potential benefits and challenges that RWA poses for mental health.

Furthermore, there is a noticeable absence of policy recommendations on how to support the mental health of individuals engaged in RWA. As the formalization of RWA into policies is relatively new for most countries, the effectiveness of these policies and the identification of additional policies that could support mental health in the context of RWA remain unclear and under-researched.

6.2. Gaps in economic impacts of RWA

Willingness for RWA

The literature on remote work often fails to differentiate between factors related to a worker's choice to work remotely and those related to their ability to do so. This distinction is crucial for better understanding the mechanisms behind the adoption of remote work. Although there is extensive literature on the usage and determinants of remote work, to our knowledge, there are very few studies specifically addressing WFS or WFA arrangements.

Willingness to offer RWA

The existing research on employers' willingness to adopt RWA has notable gaps, particularly concerning the extent and inclusiveness of RWA offered by employers. Much of the current literature focuses on the extensive margin, but there is a need to explore the intensive margins more thoroughly. Additionally, the dynamics between employee and employer preferences and the influence of labour and product market conditions on these preferences are not well understood. Factors such as labour shortages, competitors' remote work policies, and whether markets are driven by price or quality competition could significantly impact employer attitudes towards RWA. To bridge these knowledge gaps, future studies should employ comprehensive firm surveys and ensure diverse sampling across various sectors and regions.

Organizational support

To the best of our knowledge, the existing literature on organizational support for remote work is relatively limited. The studies conducted so far have not explored the potential combinations of managerial practices; instead, they focus on identifying individual practices that contribute to effective remote work. Additionally, these studies do not account for the diversity of practices implemented, which can vary based on the characteristics of the company or the country being studied.

Productivity

Research on the long-term effects of RWA on productivity is still limited, particularly as hybrid work models become increasingly prevalent. There is a call for more extensive studies to assess the productivity impacts of RWA across various job roles and industries. From a firm perspective, there is a significant need for firm-level surveys to collect data on employer perspectives and organizational outcomes. These surveys could help understand how management practices, corporate culture, technological investments, and macroeconomic factors like labour market competition affect the effectiveness of RWA. Additionally, there is a need to explore specific managerial practices and leadership styles that could boost productivity and satisfaction among remote workers. The influence of different office settings on remote work adaptability and productivity also requires further investigation.

From an individual perspective, while surveys are commonly used to measure employee productivity, they only provide a snapshot in time and fail to capture productivity fluctuations throughout the day or in different settings. Alternatives such as time diaries could offer a more detailed view of productivity variations across locations and times. Moreover, longitudinal studies could provide deeper insights into the long-term effects of RWA, including potential risks like burnout, stress, and social isolation, which could offset the productivity benefits of remote working.

RWA and digital up-skilling

The literature examining the link between remote work and digital up-skilling is sparse and often focuses on specific demographics or regions, lacking a broader perspective. Most studies do not differentiate between types of digital skills, treating them generally, which may obscure how remote work impacts different digital competencies. Additionally, much of the research has been conducted during periods of confinement, questioning the applicability of findings in less restrictive remote working environments. There is a need for more comprehensive research to understand the various mechanisms, such as employer-sponsored training or mentoring, that facilitate digital up-skilling in remote work settings.

Willingness to offer RWA as a recruitment tool to deal with skills shortage

There is a limited amount of empirical evidence on the strategic use of RWA by firms as a tool to address local skills shortages. Existing studies tend to focus on specific subsets of firms based on location, industry, or size, and often involve a small number of observations, making it difficult to generalize findings. This has resulted in several knowledge gaps that need to be explored in future research. Conducting large-scale, representative surveys of firms could provide deeper insights into the factors that influence the use of RWA and the various strategies firms employ to mitigate skills shortages. Such surveys could also reveal how these strategies differ based on firm characteristics and local labour market conditions. Understanding how firms actively use RWA to manage local skill shortages is crucial for comprehending the broader economic impacts of expanding local labour markets.

RWA impacts on wages

Despite extensive pre-pandemic research the wage impacts of RWA, several knowledge gaps persist, particularly in the post-covid era. The adoption of remote work technologies and the broader acceptance of RWA since the pandemic suggest that their wage effects might differ from those observed pre-covid. However, there is a lack of evidence on these post-covid wage effects and an insufficient understanding of how different types of RWA, such as WFH versus WFA, uniquely impact wages.

The literature also reveals notable gender-based inequalities. While gender disparities have been well-documented, other forms of inequality based on race, ethnicity, and socio-economic status are less studied. RWA have the potential to promote wage equity, but their effects are influenced by various factors such as firm size, job type, and demographic and household characteristics. The long-term effects of RWA on career progression and job satisfaction also remain underexplored. Addressing these gaps could provide a more nuanced understanding of how RWAs shape the labour market and affect various worker demographics.

Additionally, there is a scarcity of firm-level surveys that assess the impact of RWA. Such surveys could offer valuable insights into organizational policies, managerial practices, and their effects on wage outcomes. They could also help identify specific characteristics that influence the uptake and success of RWA, thereby enhancing our understanding of their broader impacts.

Cross-border tax and transfer arrangements

Understanding the impact of RWA on taxes, social security, and labour law is crucial for policymakers, cross-border workers, and their employers. Cross-border work introduces complexities due to the lack of coordination between different national laws in these areas. This discoordination can lead to issues, particularly in cross-border situations where different conflict rules apply. For instance, while social security in some countries is funded through taxation, this arrangement can create complications in cross-border scenarios.

A significant challenge is that policymakers may focus solely on one legal area without considering the interconnectedness of these laws. Changes in the conflict rules of social security, for example, are not isolated and have broader implications on taxation and labour laws. For cross-border workers, it is essential to understand how working from home affects their tax obligations and net income. Similarly, employers need clarity on these issues to manage their workforce effectively.

However, there is a notable gap in the availability of relevant and up-to-date information for all parties involved. Additionally, there is a lack of precise data on the number of cross-border workers, which varies significantly between states. Some states have generalized data that does not specifically address cross-border employment, impacting the accuracy of budgetary forecasts related to changes in taxation and social security rules. This lack of data underscores the need for better information systems to support informed decision-making by policymakers, employers, and workers in the context of cross-border work.

Policy and regulatory gaps in economic impacts

The existing policy reports on RWA delve into various impacts such as productivity, working conditions, work-life balance, and inequalities. However, there is a significant gap in empirical evidence regarding the outcomes of regulations previously implemented to manage these remote work setups. This gap underscores the need for rigorous evaluation of such regulations across different countries to derive more universally applicable insights, rather than conclusions limited by specific regional contexts.

Moreover, there is a noted deficiency in standardized guidelines for assessing the feasibility of remote jobs across different regions and sectors, particularly where digital infrastructure is lacking. Current regulations fall short in promoting the adoption of

technologies that not only facilitate remote work but also ensure data security and privacy. The focus tends to be on the immediate technical feasibility of remote work, often overlooking the long-term effects on job quality and career progression.

Additionally, there is a call for policies that support continuous professional development and ensure equal opportunities for career advancement in remote roles. The reports also emphasize the need for a common terminology for RWA, pointing out that the absence of a universal definition leads to inconsistencies in research and literature, which could be mitigated by establishing a standardized terminology. This would help in reducing discrepancies and enhancing the clarity and effectiveness of research and policies concerning remote work arrangements.

6.3. Gaps in spatial and environmental impacts of RWA

Impact of RWA for travel behaviour

The existing literature on the impacts of RWA on travel behaviour primarily focuses on general trends, with less attention given to variations across different geographic regions, urban types, vulnerable societal groups, or the nature of remote work (full-time vs part-time, WFH vs WFA). Additionally, there is a notable gap in research from the perspective of employers, which could complement the employee-focused findings. Current studies often measure RWA by the number of days worked remotely, but incorporating the number of hours could provide a more nuanced understanding of RWA's impact. There is also potential for exploring how RWA interacts with urban planning efforts aimed at reducing car dependency and enhancing sustainable mobility. Comparisons between remote and non-remote workers within the same demographic segments are also underexplored, suggesting a need for survey questions on past behaviour to better understand shifts in travel behaviour. Methodologically, the literature could benefit from incorporating qualitative research methods, such as in-depth interviews and focus groups, to gain deeper insights into individual experiences. Moreover, standardizing data collection methods across studies could improve the ability to compare and generalize findings.

Impact of RWA for daily activities

The literature on the impact of RWA on daily activities lacks direct insights from key stakeholders like employers and retailers, which could enrich understanding of RWA's effects. Current studies often rely on data from single-day analyses, such as surveys or travel diaries, which may not fully capture the ongoing impact of RWA. To overcome these limitations, future research should consider longitudinal studies or foresight methods to assess long-term effects. Additionally, expanding research to cover various geographical areas, including rural and cross-border regions, and diverse

demographic groups, like senior workers and different genders, could provide a deeper, more comprehensive insight into RWA's broader implications.

Employees' willingness to relocate residences

The understanding of how RWA influence employees' residential location choices has expanded since the COVID-19 pandemic, yet significant gaps remain. Current knowledge does not adequately compare the weight of remote work as a decision factor against other considerations like housing characteristics (size, cost, type) and neighbourhood attributes (proximity to workplace, public transport, and natural spaces). Stated Preference experiments could shed light on these dynamics. Additionally, the causality between remote work and residential choices is unclear. It is uncertain whether remote work drives changes in residential location or if the choice of residence influences the extent of remote work. Addressing these questions necessitates more longitudinal studies that track employee biographies to understand these relationships better.

Employees' willingness to relocate workplaces

The impact of RWA on employees' workplace location choices has primarily been studied in the context of choosing between the office, home, or alternative locations like coffee shops or co-working spaces. However, there is a lack of research on whether remote work prompts employees to reconsider their job choices entirely. Specifically, it is unclear to what extent remote work enables employees to access a broader range of job opportunities, potentially allowing them to accept positions from employers located much further away than would be feasible if they were required to work on-site.

Employers' willingness to downsize and/or relocate offices

Our understanding of the impact of RWA on employers' location choices is primarily limited to studies focusing on decisions to downsize office space and adopt more flexible use of existing workspaces. To date, there is no comprehensive knowledge on the extent to which remote work influences employers to completely reconsider the geographical location of their offices. Given the concern that companies may relocate away from urban centres as remote work persists, it is crucial to conduct further research that explores the significance of remote work as a location factor in comparison to traditional factors such as company size, cost, accessibility by car or public transport, and proximity to employees.

Physical activity

In our literature review concerning RWA and physical activity, we found that most studies have concentrated on the effects of lockdown policies on physical activity levels. Only a few studies have compared physical activity levels between working from home and working from the office during the same time period. Additionally, these studies typically rely on self-reported data on physical activity, with less attention given to physical activity resulting from active (or inactive) commuting. While these studies offer valuable insights into the shift from commute-based travel to discretionary trips, they only begin to explore the potential impacts of remote working arrangements on physical activity. Clearly, more research is necessary to fully understand these dynamics.

Emissions

From our literature review on studies estimating the potential for greenhouse gas emissions reductions through the implementation of RWA, a significant research gap identified is the need for a more holistic and comprehensive approach. This includes accounting for higher-order “rebound” effects and gaining a deeper understanding of the conditions and factors that contribute to reduced emissions. However, accurately capturing or estimating these factors and effects presents numerous challenges. These challenges encompass understanding the full socio-economic context, including interactions with other household members, capturing additional non-work trips and the transport modes used, and accurately recording additional activities during RWA and their energy intensity. Additionally, it is crucial to determine under what conditions RWA can result in net energy savings for employers and how to limit additional energy consumption in the employee's workspace. Accurately modelling the broader societal impacts of reducing road traffic during peak commuting hours, including effects on the public transport system, and understanding the longer-term effects of RWA, particularly concerning the relocation of employees and employers, are also essential. Since most studies have relied on modelling effects from hypothetical scenarios, conducting a longitudinal study could provide a better understanding of changes in habits and context before and after implementing an RWA policy in a specific work environment.

Socio-spatial inequality due to RWA

There is very limited knowledge about how the increasing adoption of RWA influences residential relocation and its subsequent effects on societal structures, particularly concerning spatial segregation and social inequality. This issue stems from the structural inequality linked to the teleworkability of jobs, raising critical questions about how RWA-induced residential relocations are reshaping population compositions at neighbourhood and city levels.

Despite the significance of these questions, none of the studies we reviewed specifically address this issue. A few discursive articles touch upon changes in urban spaces and spatial inequality, offering predictions for future developments. However, initial studies post-COVID-19 indicate that spatial changes are occurring, though the findings are often contradictory. This underscores the need for more comprehensive research that delves into the implications for the social fabric and spatial inequalities at neighbourhood, city, regional, and global levels.

The lack of knowledge in this area can be attributed to two main factors. Firstly, there is a methodological gap – no comprehensive large-scale surveys currently exist that explicitly inquire about the reasons behind residential relocations, including information on individuals' previous and current residences. Secondly, there is a general lack of interest – most large-scale studies that indirectly estimate the impact of RWA on housing markets primarily focus on economic implications, such as property and rental prices, rather than social outcomes.

Cross-border mobility

The impact of RWA on mobility in cross-border areas seems to represent an unexplored field of research. Given the differences in taxation and social security between cross-border workers and local residents, it is crucial to broaden the scope of investigation beyond the impact of WFH and also encompass other forms of RWA, such as the use of satellite offices. This expanded focus is essential because cross-border workers may face unique challenges and opportunities that differ significantly from those of local residents, influencing their work arrangements and mobility patterns. Understanding these dynamics can provide valuable insights into the socio-economic impacts of RWA on cross-border regions and help policymakers design more effective and inclusive strategies.

Digital nomadism and gentrification

Only a small number of articles address the topic of digital nomadism and gentrification. Thus, to better assess the effects of digital nomads on socio-spatial changes (such as gentrification), it is necessary to fill at least some gaps in knowledge, such as: Which physical-spatial changes can be observed with the gradual increase in digital nomads, in addition to the economic changes already recorded? Which effects does the notable rise in digital nomads – many of whom come from places with better living standards and pay – have on the towns that draw them? How much of an impact do these remote workers have on the escalating cost of living and the quickening pace of gentrification? And what impact does the increasing number of remote workers and digital nomads have on cities, particularly ones like Lisbon that already struggle with gentrification and housing issues?

Furthermore, the articles reviewed have gaps in methodology and sample size, which are important to recognize and avoid in future research. It is evident that remote work and digital nomads significantly influence urban spaces and socioeconomic conditions. While digital nomads can enhance their own quality of life, and their presence can lead to some economic benefits, it can also lead to increased living costs and gentrification in host cities, potentially displacing local residents. Future studies should investigate the long-term effects of digital nomads on the areas they inhabit to better understand these impacts.

Multi-locality and second homes

The literature on the impacts of RWA on multi-locality is limited, particularly when considering working from second homes and summer cottages. Furthermore, most studies are conducted within the context of Nordic countries. There are significant knowledge gaps concerning the economic and social dimensions of multi-locality, including questions about whether RWA can revitalize rural municipalities and how, the opportunities for rural areas in implementing RWA infrastructure, whether RWA can reduce spatial inequalities, and how locals perceive second-home residents who might use the public services of the municipality without contributing to its tax base.

Additionally, RWA has the potential to influence movement and migration patterns, possibly reducing the need for working-age individuals to relocate to larger cities, enabling parents with young children to raise them in smaller communities, and encouraging more people to work from second homes for extended periods, particularly during the summer months. Therefore, RWA could potentially counteract the megatrend of urbanization. However, longitudinal research is necessary to determine whether these effects are significant and long-lasting or minor and temporary.

7. Conceptual diagram

In this chapter, we present updated versions of the conceptual diagram developed in the WinWin4WorkLife Grant Agreement. These diagrams present the different dimensions, causal relationships, and influential factors in relation to the impacts of RWA. The overarching purpose of the following conceptual diagrams is to illustrate this complex system and reveal the “truth” of all relationships presented, following the upcoming data collection and data analysis of the WinWin4WorkLife project.

Firstly, we present a simplified conceptual diagram to briefly illustrate the main components of the RWA impacts and different interrelations (Figure 3). Secondly, two other diagrams depict employees’ (Figure 4) and employers’ (Figure 5) perspectives in more detail. Figure 6 then unveils the long-term impacts (end-goals) of RWA for employers and employees, and finally, Figure 7 conceptualises all of these relationships in relation to policies.

The simplified conceptual illustration presented in Figure 3 shows that employer and employee circumstances and characteristics interact, influence, and are influenced by all three spheres of long-term impacts – societal, environmental, and economic – formulating and defining different RWA policies.

Figure 3: Simplified conceptual diagram.

Employee circumstances are the starting and central point of this chain and of the WinWin4WorkLife concept: personal, work-related, and spatial circumstances create the conditions for various RWA experiences, which in turn lead to personal impacts of RWA in terms of higher or lower life satisfaction, work satisfaction, and spatial satisfaction – this outcome is usually referred to as work-life balance. These personal RWA impacts and their characteristics will in turn lead to wider long-term impacts in terms of (i) physical and mental health of the workforce, (ii) the ability to alleviate existing inequalities (in terms of income, skills, gender, etc.), and (iii) support for processes of urban-rural regeneration along more sustainable and resilient patterns of spatial development and mobility (Figure 4). In short, the initial circumstances of the employees influence their experiences with RWA, which in turn impact various elements across all three spheres. Figure 4 also features feedback loops, showing that the impacts can loop back to influence RWA experiences and circumstances, demonstrating a dynamic and interconnected system.

Figure 4: Part of the conceptual diagram capturing employee's perspective.

Employee RWA influence and are strongly influenced by employer practices, characterised by their existing regulations and internal culture (particularly organisational support for remote work), and have important implications for efficiency and productivity, access and retention of skills, operational costs and the company's own environmental footprint (Figure 5). Characteristics of the employer influence their practices related to RWA, which in turn impact various outcomes for the workforce and society. Similar to Figure 4, Figure 5 shows that impacts can loop

back to influence RWA practices and employer characteristics, demonstrating the complexity of the system.

Figure 5: Part of the conceptual diagram capturing employer's perspective.

The WinWin4WorkLife project aims to create positive policy synergies in achieving personally healthy, socially inclusive, and environmentally sustainable RWA practices in Europe for employees and employers (Figure 6). These represent the expected long-term impacts of the project as shown in Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5. As shown in Figure 6, each of these three dimensions within the long-term impacts encompasses various elements. It is within the scope of this project to explore and analyse which elements impact RWA and how, and what is their importance.

Figure 6: Long term impacts of RWA for employer in (a) and employee in (b).

In terms of policies and regulations, these are applicable to a multilevel governance in several areas, ranging from the employer level to the EU level, encompassing broader social, economic, and environmental issues (Figure 7). Each concentric circle in Figure 7 represents a different level of scope, starting from the innermost circle (employer level) and expanding outwards indicating a growing geographical scale. Such policies influence and are influenced by both employees and employers which are also interacting with each other. They aim to intervene on all three spheres in a holistic and integrated way and at different levels along the causal chain and its feedback loops.

Figure 7: Policy concept

8. Conclusion

In this systematic literature review, we have explored the multifaceted impacts of remote work across various spheres including the private, work, and spatial domains. The review delves into how remote work affects mental health, social dynamics, economic factors, and environmental considerations, covering the benefits and challenges of remote work, including its influence on gender disparities, digital skills, productivity, urban-rural dynamics, and more. Moreover, we have discussed the need for targeted policies and further research to optimize remote work practices and mitigate its negative consequences. This comprehensive review provides insights into the evolving landscape of remote work and its broader implications. We synthesize the results of the review below.

Social and cultural impacts of remote work on the private sphere

Remote work can impact mental health and well-being both positively and negatively. Factors such as work overload, increased working hours, technostress, and work-family conflict can contribute to negative outcomes. However, several factors contribute positively to the well-being of remote workers, including flexibility in work arrangements, adequacy of equipment, effective communication, supportive leadership, and assistance from colleagues.

Remote work also impacts both objectively and subjectively experienced time. Studies show a shift in duration and timing of work during remote workdays with less time spent on work, and less during core work hours. WFH generally increases multitasking and fragmentation of time-use and this in turn increases feelings of time pressure.

Remote work generates major social tensions by mixing the personal and professional spheres and rhythms. The hybrid dimension of remote work is likely to generate a degree of discomfort for remote workers, depending in particular on arrangements within the household but also with employers. Remote work is also a factor in renegotiating the division of labour and domestic arrangements. It can therefore be a resource for renewing personal and professional arrangements while improving employees' quality of life.

Gender disparities persist in remote working environments, with women, particularly mothers, facing greater challenges in balancing family responsibilities with work demands. Women experience remote work as less favourable than men, yet women more often use it to align work with family responsibilities. This imbalance can lead to increased stress and reduced well-being among female remote workers.

Some regulations in EU states focus on the mental health impacts of remote work and how to mitigate these impacts, but in general, mental health does not seem to be a focus point on policies regarding remote work. This is the case for both national

policies and policies from EU bodies and organisations, although the “right to disconnect” has been implemented in some member states.

Economic impacts of remote work on the work sphere

Remote work is positively correlated with digital up-skilling, with some variation according to the socio-demographic characteristics of remote workers. Women, older, and highly educated remote workers demonstrated a greater increase in digital skills during the COVID-19 pandemic than other remote workers. After the pandemic, employees have generally expressed a desire to continue working remotely two to three days a week. The desire to work remotely varies according to employees' socio-demographic characteristics, their home-work commute, and their perception of their productivity when working remotely, as well as the managerial practices put in place by their employer. The teleworkability of jobs varies widely across sectors, regions, and socio-economic groups. Jobs in finance and ICT are highly remotable, while those in construction and retail are not. Factors like gender, income, and education also play a role, with higher-income, better-educated workers, and women more likely to have remotable jobs. Low-skilled, low-income, and part-time workers face significant challenges, making them more vulnerable during crises like COVID-19. Addressing these disparities requires targeted policies to enhance teleworkability and reduce inequalities.

The pandemic has shifted employer attitudes and practices towards remote work and the post-covid regime is characterised by a widespread use of remote work, especially in a hybrid form. Studies support the notion that firms use RWA to attract and retain employees. In particular, firms increasingly use RWA as a strategy to overcome local skills shortages and to expand the geography of their talent pool. To avoid skills shortages, firms also use RWA to keep highly valued employees whose skills might be difficult to be replaced by new hires. Still, there is a lack of research on what determines the extent and comprehensiveness of RWA that employers are willing to offer.

Remote work also presents new challenges for firms, including a greater distance between managers and their subordinates and a potential feeling of loneliness among remote workers. In response to these challenges, firms are implementing management policies to support remote work and ensure the productivity and well-being of remote workers.

The impacts of remote work on firms' productivity are generally positive, yet they come with challenges. Significant influences include management practices, employee well-being, and technological adaptation. Each of these factors plays a crucial role in determining productivity outcomes in remote work environments. As organizations continue to adapt to the evolving work landscape, understanding and optimizing these factors will be essential for maximizing the benefits of remote work.

Moreover, remote work has significant impacts on wages, with notable inequalities, particularly along gender lines. While RWA hold potential for promoting wage equity,

their effects are mediated by a range of factors, including firm size, job type, and demographic as well as household characteristics. The literature on RWA and taxation also highlights the inadequacy of the current regulation. Coordination between taxation and social security contributions is crucial, yet the unclear tax consequences of RWA could hinder the adoption of remote working for cross-border workers and their employers, which is why improvements in coordinating of taxation and social security are needed.

A rising number of policy reports by bodies such as Eurofound, the EU Commission, the ILO, and the OECD focus on the economic impacts of remote work. They cover many policy-relevant aspects of the recent shift towards flexible work arrangements, including productivity, working conditions, work-life balance, and various forms of inequalities. The reports provide policymakers with empirical evidence to make informed decisions about the need for regulation in the changing world of work.

Spatial and environmental impacts of remote work on cities and rural areas

Research on remote work and travel behaviour shows mixed results regarding trip duration, frequency, and sustainable transportation use. Remote work can reduce commuting distances, potentially lowering greenhouse gas emissions. However, the overall impact is nuanced due to rebound effects such as increased non-work trips, higher energy use at remote work locations, and relocation to more car-dependent areas. Advanced simulations indicate that any direct travel reductions from remote working are counterbalanced by rebound effects, suggesting little support for RWA in promoting sustainable travel patterns. To achieve overall energy savings, RWA should be paired with technological investments and urban re-densification strategies.

Remote work also has a structural effect on the social fabric and spatial inequalities at the neighbourhood, city, regional, and global levels. However, there is a lack of empirical knowledge. To mitigate the knowledge gap on how remote work impacts spatial inequalities (e.g., segregation and regional disparity), future research should explicitly collect relevant input data, estimate potential spatial inequalities based on people's willingness and preferences for residential relocation, and incorporate neighbourhood social composition characteristics into housing market prediction models.

In particular, digital nomads influence urban spaces and their socioeconomic conditions significantly. While the lifestyle of digital nomads can offer personal financial benefits, their presence in cities can lead to increased living costs, promote gentrification, and potentially displace local residents. These effects necessitate a thorough investigation focused on the long-term impacts that digital nomads have on the communities where they reside. Understanding these implications is crucial to addressing the challenges and opportunities that arise from the growing trend of digital nomadism in urban environments.

Finally, remote work facilitates multi-local living, which has the potential to impact the megatrend of urbanization if city residents move to rural areas for extended periods or even permanently. RWA such as coworking spaces offer opportunities for rural municipalities grappling with declining and aging populations. However, longitudinal research is necessary to determine whether remote work can effectively address these issues.

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Annex 1

For the systematic literature review, we performed a total of 24 separate search queries regarding three main impact areas of RWA in the Scopus database:

Table A1. Search queries for the social and cultural impacts of RWA.

Burnout, stress, loneliness, isolation, and inequalities
("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (employee OR individual OR personnel OR staff OR team OR worker OR company OR corporation OR employer OR enterprise OR firm OR mnc OR mne OR multinational OR organization) AND (loneliness OR stress OR isolation OR burnout OR "mental health" OR mental OR psychological OR "well being" OR wellbeing)
Quality of time
("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (employee OR individual OR personnel OR staff OR team OR worker) AND ("time use" OR "time budget" OR "time allocation" OR "time demands" OR "time constraints" OR "time scheduling" OR "quality of time" OR "contamination of time" OR "time contamination" OR "intensification of time" OR "spill over of time" OR "intensity of time" OR "temporal contamination" OR "temporal intensity" OR "acceleration of time" OR "temporal acceleration" OR "lack of time" OR "time deep*" OR "time creep" OR "time pressure" OR "time poverty" OR "time satisfaction" OR "temporal satisfaction" OR "time squeeze" OR "time compression" OR "time slippage" OR "time scarcity" OR "time crunch" OR "multitasking" OR "uninterrupted time" OR "feeling rushed" OR "pressed for time")
Daily rhythms and household task arrangements
("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (employee OR individual OR personnel OR staff OR team OR worker) AND ("households" OR "arrangement" OR "fragmentation" OR "tasks")

Table A2. Search queries for the economic impacts of RWA.

Willingness for RWA
("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (employee OR individual OR personnel OR staff OR team OR worker) AND (uptake OR preferences OR eligibility OR adoption)
Willingness to offer RWA
("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (company OR corporation OR employer OR enterprise OR firm OR mnc OR mne OR multinational OR organization) AND (uptake OR willing* OR offer OR opportunity OR enable OR allow OR accept)
Organizational support
("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (company OR corporation OR employer OR enterprise OR firm OR mnc OR mne OR multinational OR organization) AND ("organizational support" OR "health and safety" OR "wages" OR "working time" OR "job security" OR "training and development" OR "benefits" OR "hierarchy levels" OR "monitoring policy" OR "human resources management")
Employee productivity
("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (employee OR individual OR personnel OR staff OR team OR worker) AND ("productivity")
Employers' concerns about their workforce productivity
("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (company OR corporation OR employer OR enterprise OR firm OR mnc OR mne OR multinational OR organization) AND (productivity OR output OR employment OR {firm-level effect*} OR outcome OR profit OR revenue)
RWA and digital up-skilling
("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (employee OR individual OR personnel OR staff OR team OR worker) AND ("digital skills" OR "digital upskilling" OR "digital divide")

Willingness to offer RWA as a recruitment tool

("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (company OR corporation OR employer OR enterprise OR firm OR mnc OR mne OR multinational OR organization) AND (shortage* OR skill OR recruit* OR hire OR hiring)

RWA impacts on wage offers

("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (company OR corporation OR employer OR enterprise OR firm OR mnc OR mne OR multinational OR organization) AND (wage OR {wage offer*} OR salary OR pay OR reward)

Cross-border tax and transfer arrangements

("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND ({tax} OR taxation OR "social security")

Table A3. Search queries for the spatial and environmental impacts of RWA.

Impact of RWA on travel behaviour
("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND ("travel behaviour" OR travel* OR "transport mode" OR transport* OR mobility OR "distance travel*")
Impact of RWA on daily activities
("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (activit* OR "e-shopping" OR "e-leisure" OR telemedicine) AND (attitudes OR intention OR participation OR behavior OR rural* OR fragmentation OR substitution OR complementarity OR modification)
Employees' willingness to relocate residences: residential relocation
("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (relocate OR relocation OR downsize)
Employees' willingness to relocate residences: residential preferences
("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND ("residential preference*")
Employees' willingness to relocate workplaces
("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (employee OR individual OR personnel OR staff OR team OR worker) AND (workplace OR "work location" OR "job change")
Employers' willingness to downsize and/or relocate offices
("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (company OR corporation OR employer OR enterprise OR firm OR mnc OR mne OR multinational OR organization) AND ("office relocation" OR "office location" OR "office space" OR "location decisions" OR "reorganization of office space" OR "office space needs" OR "adoption of new working spaces")
Physical activity
("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR

<p>"multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND ("inhalation rates while travelling" OR "injury risk while travelling" OR "physical activity")</p>
<p>Emissions</p>
<p>("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (noise OR air OR emission*)</p>
<p>Spatial segregation and social inequality due to RWA</p>
<p>("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (segregat* OR "spatial inequality" OR "social inequality" OR "socio-spatial inequality" OR "socio-spatial inequality" OR "spatial isolation" OR "socio-economic inequality" OR "socioeconomic inequality" OR "urban inequality" OR "regional inequality" OR "spatial polarization" OR "socio-spatial polarization" OR "socio-spatial polarization" OR "social polarization")</p>
<p>Cross-border mobility</p>
<p>("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (cross-border)</p>
<p>Digital nomadism and gentrification</p>
<p>("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR "second home" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND (gentrification OR territory OR lisbon)</p>
<p>Multi-locality and second homes</p>
<p>("co-working space" OR "coworking space" OR "digital nomad*" OR "digital workplace" OR "distance work*" OR "distributed work" OR {e-work} OR {e-working} OR "flexible work" OR "flexible workplace" OR "home-based work" OR "home office" OR "hybrid work" OR "location-independent work" OR "mobile office" OR "mobile work" OR "multi-locat* work" OR "remote job" OR "remote work" OR "satellite office" OR telecommut* OR telework* OR "virtual work" OR "work* from anywhere" OR "work* from home" OR workation OR workcation) AND ("second home" OR "multi-locat*" OR multiloca*)</p>